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DELIVRABLE 7.2: Report on classical and next generation models of soil organic carbon dynamic

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WP 7: Multivariate analysis and modelling soil organic matter dynamics

Task 7.2. Modelling soil organic matter dynamics

- Subtask 7.2.1. Exploring new modelling solutions
- Sub-task 7.2.2. Improving classical models

Table of contents

List of Figures	5
List of Tables	10
1 Introduction and methodology	11
2 Review of soil organic matter and carbon models: Key considerations for model selection	14
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 Method.....	14
2.2.1 Different scales of study.....	15
2.2.1.1 Time scale and carbon recalcitrance.....	15
2.2.1.2 Spatial scale.....	18
2.2.2 Important factor and process represented in models.....	21
2.2.2.1 SOM and SOC compartmentation pools (all WP).....	21
2.2.2.2 Microbial activity and diversity (WP2, WP4, WP6).....	23
2.2.2.3 Plant activity and diversity (WP2).....	26
2.2.2.4 Meso- macro-fauna activity and diversity (WP3).....	28
2.2.2.5 Nitrogen, other nutrient cycles and chemical elements (WP5).....	29
2.2.2.6 Soil structure, Aggregates and physical/chemical protection (WP6).....	32
2.3 Discussion and Conclusion	34
3 Integrating new process to improve SOC dynamics representation by using simple models.....	36
3.1 Introduction	36
3.2 Method.....	36
3.2.1 Modeling framework and bank of mechanistic models	36
3.2.2 Meteo data.....	37
3.2.3 SYMHONY, a microbial-driven SOM model.	38
3.2.4 ModVege, an above-ground plant model.....	40
3.2.5 Nitrogen fixation, implementation of a new function related to diversity	42
3.2.6 DYNAGRAM and COSMO, plant diversity interactions models	44

3.2.7	The Belowground biomass	46
3.2.8	Coupling process	46
3.3	Results	50
3.3.1	Biomass simulation	50
3.3.2	SOM and SOC annual dynamics	53
3.3.3	Nitrogen fixation effect	57
3.4	Discussion and Conclusion	59
3.4.1	Encouraging results and critical point of progress.....	59
3.4.2	Working in progress with root addition	60
3.4.3	For the future, legumes and plant trait distribution.....	61
3.4.4	Acknowledgment	61
4	Adapting the classical model RothC.....	62
4.1	Introduction	62
4.2	Materials & Methods.....	63
4.2.1	Modelling Strategy	63
4.2.2	Soil sampling along a European gradient.....	64
4.2.3	Description of LTE for modelling.....	65
4.2.3.1	<i>LTE Tillage and Cover Crops (Lithuania).....</i>	<i>65</i>
4.2.3.2	<i>LTE Clever Cover Cropping (The Netherlands).....</i>	<i>66</i>
4.2.3.3	<i>LTE Organic Matter (Belgium).....</i>	<i>67</i>
4.2.3.4	<i>New Experimental Field Fungi and Cover Cropping System (Turkey)</i>	<i>68</i>
4.3	Results and Discussion.....	69
4.3.1	Assessment of optimal Rate Modifying Factor	69
4.3.2	Exploring relationships between optimal RMF and indicators soil microbiome	73
4.3.3	Impact assessment	74
4.4	Discussion	75
4.5	Conclusion	76
4.6	Acknowledgement.....	76

5. References..... 77

List of Figures

- Figure 1 :** Non-exhaustive examples of relationships and dependencies of factors and processes to our two main objectives of plant productivity (s) and greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation. Colors refer to other work packages (WP) of the AGROECOSeqC project that will shape our work (see Figure 2). Anthropogenic activities are not placed on this graph because we consider it playing a role on every of those components. 11
- Figure 2 :** Mind map of other working packages of the AGROECOSeqC project that will frame our work. 12
- Figure 3:** Molecular structure decomposition rate – This figure compiles data from surface horizons of 20 long-term field experiments (up to 23 years) in temperate climate, using ¹³C labelling to trace the residence time of bulk SOM and of individual molecular compounds. The variation in turnover time is also seen in the compounds of microbial origin analysed for ¹³C content, phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA) produced by Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria and amino sugars (hexosamines). For clarity, we have excluded outliers. Data points: thin horizontal lines, 10th and 90th percentiles; box, 25th and 75th percentiles; central vertical line, median. From Schmidt et Torn 2011 17
- Figure 4:** percentage of models with given spatial and temporal scales, along with the type II regression line between them (dot-dashed line; $R^2 \approx 0.45$, $P < 0.0001$). From Manzoni & Porporato 2009 17
- Figure 5:** Model classification of Powlson et al. (2013). 17
- Figure 6:** Conceptual diagram of the main interactions between soil substrates and organisms, as represented by global and continuous spatial representations. Gray and white boxes represent carbon and nitrogen compartments and fluxes respectively. The dotted lines in the SOM boxes (left) illustrate qualitatively how the substrate and decomposer variables are treated as a continuum in the Q-soil model (Ågren and Bosatta, 1996). From Manzoni & Porporato, 2009 19
- Figure 7 :** Model of pore space from 3D tomography image with – A) Perspective views of the drained pore space at –20 cm water pressures. Top left is initially water saturated pore space, top right shows border balls drained and down shows equilibrium state. Grey balls are filled with air and white balls are filled with water and B) Conceptual diagram of the model From (Monga et al., 2008) 20
- Figure 8 :** . Overview on soil C cycling in dynamic landscapes and the key mechanisms involved in C sequestration and release from soils. Processes indicated at the plateau/summit position take place along the whole hillslope, but are affected by soil redistribution. 20
- Figure 9 :** A, Based on chemical analysis of the extracted materials (Observed), the formation of humic polymers (Interpretation) was postulated to be an important source of recalcitrant SOM. B, Direct highresolution in situ observations with non-destructive techniques (Observations) have been able to explain the functional group chemistry of the extracted humic substances as relatively simple biomolecules (Interpretation), without the need to invoke the presence of unexplainable. From Schmidt et al. (2011) 22

- Figure 10 : Historic development of microbial models since 1975 (a) and (b) and percentage of microbial models with consideration of major microbial process (c). The percentage was calculated as the number of models considering each process divided by the total number of published models in each time period. From Louis et al. 2016 publication mineralization and immobilization; SIMP, simplified mineralization formulations (from Manzoni & Porporato, 2009)** 24
- Figure 11 : Flow diagram of ecosys model showing C transformations in a single substrate–microbe complex from Grant 1998. It is identified as a Functional Diversity model with 9 functional pools in Louis et al. (2016).** 25
- Figure 12 : Relational diagram of the carbon flow ($\mu\text{g C cm}^{-3}$) of the BACKWAVE model. With A_CO2 : cumulative CO2 sink to atmosphere ; BACT : total number of bacteria ; BFN : bacterial feeding nematodes ; COP : copiotrophic bacteria ; E : Enzymes ; HB : hydrolytic bacteria ; HUMOM : humus organic matter of soil ; LIRES : lignin fraction of plant residues ; OLIG : oligotrophic bacteria ; PRTZ : protozoa ; S : soluble substrate ; SOLOM : soluble organic matter of soil ; SORES : soluble plant residue ; STRES : stable fraction of plant residues ; STROM : structural organic matter of soil. Rectangles represent state variables, ovals—auxiliary variables, full lines—flows of matter (C or N), and dashed lines—flows of information. Flows of information ending in flows of matter indicate that the matter flow is influenced by the information flow. From Zelenev et al. (2006)** 25
- Figure 13 : Percentage of biogeochemical models in different model classes. M: Soil microbiology, soil aggregate, and rhizosphere models; L : Litter decomposition model; S : Soil model with no dynamic vegetation components; E : Coupled soil-plant dynamic model; G : Coupled soil-plant-atmosphere model for global applications.** 26
- Figure 14 : Main processes or filters that structure a plant community. From Lortie et al. 2004.** 27
- Figure 15 : Scale of similarities between plant groups, from simplest to most complex. Models can be developed for each level. From Wang, E., Robertson 2002.** 28
- Figure 16 : Main animal-mediated processes (boxes) affecting the eight insights (symbols) identified by Schmidt et al. (2011) that should be considered for improving SOM models. From Filser et al. 2016** 29
- Figure 17 : A resume of Soil fauna affecting formation pathways of POM and MAOM via transformation, translocation, and grazing.soil fauna effect. From Angst 2024.** 29
- Figure 18 : Percentages of models using the different N-limitation schemes (NLIM) at different spatial (e) and temporal (f) scales, including C-only (CM); no N-limitation (ND); inhibition factor (INH); Carbon losses in response to N-limitation (CO) and variable microbial or substrate C/N (CN). From Manzoni & Porporato (2009).** 30
- Figure 19: Schematic representation of the chain of biochemical nitrification and denitrification reactions (left side) and microbial respirations (right side). Mineral, liquid, and gaseous domains are separated by dashed lines. AOB, NOB, DEN, and AER stand for ammonia oxidizing bacteria, nitrite oxidizing bacteria, denitrifying bacteria, and aerobic bacteria, respectively. From Maggi et al. 2008** 30

- Figure 20 : Historic trends of the percentages of models using different mineralization pathways (MIN). DIR, MIT and PAR: direct, mineralization-immobilization turnover, and parallel schemes, respectively; MIX, other schemes with simultaneous** **31**
- Figure 21 : Historic trends of the percentages of models using the different N-limitation schemes (NLIM), including C-only models (CM). IND, no N-limitation; INH, inhibition factor; CO, carbon losses in response to N-limitation; CN, variable microbial or substrate C=N; MIX, multiple formulations are simultaneously used.** **31**
- Figure 22 : (a) ECOSSE ecosystem soil N model structure showing integration of plant-soil N cycle with multi-pool soil organic matter model and, (b) the Fixation and Uptake of Nitrogen (FUN) model flowchart with four pathways of plant N uptake (passive uptake, active uptake, biological N fixation and re-translocation). From Oshte 2009** **32**
- Figure 23 : A time line of the critical advancement in the understanding of soil organic matter-aggregation interactions. From Six et al 2004** **33**
- Figure 24 : A synopsis of eight insights, contrasting historical and emerging views of soil carbon cycling. The historical view (a) has emphasized above-ground plant carbon inputs and organic matter in the top 30 cm of soil. Stable organic matter is seen to comprise mainly selectively preserved plant inputs and de novo synthesis products like humic substances, whose chemical complexity and composition render them nearly inert relative to microbial degradation. The emerging understanding (b) is that the molecular structure of organic material does not necessarily determine its stability in soil (1; molecular structure). Rather, SOM cycling is governed by multiple processes (5) shaped by environmental conditions (such as physical heterogeneity). Plant roots and rhizosphere inputs (4; roots) make a large contribution to SOM, which is mainly partial degradation and microbial products and fire residues (3) rather than humic substances (2). The vulnerability of deep soil carbon (6; deep carbon) to microbial degradation (8; soil micro-organisms) in a changing environment, such as thawing permafrost (7; thawing permafrost) remains a key uncertainty. From Schmidt et Torn 2011** **34**
- Figure 25, A: Climatic data from Jouven et al. (2006) on Marcenat INRAe research station, Auvergne, altitude 1100 m a.s.l) : mean daily temperature (solid line) and monthly precipitation(bars) with their standard deviation, on 8 years (1993-2000).** **38**
- Figure 26 : SYMPHONY conceptual diagram with state variables (rectangles), fluxes (circles) of carbon (blue) and nitrogen (red), and incoming and outgoing fluxes (clouds). The images help to understand the state variable concerned.** **38**
- Figure 27 : Conceptual scheme ModVege model with state variables (rectangles), flows (circles and arrows) of biomass (solid arrows) and informative (dotted arrows), response functions (diamonds) and input data (octagons). Images help to understand the state variable concerned.** **40**
- Figure 28 : Advantage in terms of nitrogen nutrition Nitrogen used by legumes (red solid line) and grasses (black solid line), fixed by legumes (red dashed line) and taken up by legumes (red dotted line) as a function of mineral nitrogen present in the soil A) with 500 kg.ha-1 of biomass and B) with 1500 kg.ha-1 of biomass.** **44**

Figure 29 : Flowchart of the CoSMo approach for community simulation; M indicates the number of species present in the community. From (Confalonieri, 2014)	45
Figure 30 : Structure of the DynaGraM model. Rectangular plain boxes denote state variables (plant biomass, nitrogen and water reserve); rounded rectangles account for forcing variables (climate and management), intermediate variables (LAI, growth rates) or synthetic index of diversity (Simpson evenness EB); blue plain lines denote primary relations or effects and red dashed lines denote reducer effects limiting the plant growth. From (Moulin et al., 2021)	46
Figure 31 : Conceptual diagram of the ModVege - SYMPHONY model [final coupling] with state variables (rectangles), biomass (whole arrows) and information (dotted arrows) flows (circles and arrows), response functions (diamonds), input data (octagons). Images help to understand the state variable concerned.	47
Figure 32 : Biomass of the 4 compartments (BGV, BGR, BDV et BDR) on 8 climatic year using data from the Marcenat station from 1993 to 2000, without mowing by A) ModVege B) ModVege – SYMPHONY and by adding a fertilisation of 100 kg.ha ⁻¹ by day to remove nitrogen limitation present in C) ModVege – SYMPHONY. And with mowing on days 181, 237 and 303, without fertilization by F) ModVege G) ModVege – SYMPHONY. Parameters used and initial values are those from sensibility analysis of Jouven et al. (2006a). NB: fertilization apply rate in this case is just to make appear the strong limitation of nitrogen in our model, it is not realistic.	52
Figure 33 : Growth difference between ModVege and ModVege-SYMPHONY. If the curve is < 0, it means growth is higher in ModVege-SYMPHONY, if it is > 0 it means growth is higher in ModVege and if curve = 0, ModVege and ModVege-SYMPHONY growth are equal. Without mowing and without fertilization	53
Figure 34 : NI of ModVege (dotted black line) and variable NI of ModVege- SYMPHONY mean (dark green), median (clear green), quantile 25% and quantile 75% (dotted red line inferior and superior respectively) during a mean climatic year (mean of 8 climatic years). Without mowing and without fertilization.	53
Figure 35 : evolution of SOM (kg/ha) (A&C), SOM builders, SOM decomposer and mineral N (B&C) on 3*8 climatic year in two management situation (explained in subtitles).	54
Figure 36 : evolution of FOM in two management case (A&B) on 3*8 climatic years	55
Figure 37 : Evolution of biomass (kg.ha ⁻¹) on 8 years climatic data with mowing on day 181, 237 and 303 (C&D) , different set of parameters for N fixation (kfix and efix, see Eq. 7) and percentages of legumes.	57
Figure 38 : evolution of SOM (kg/ha) (A&C), SOM builders, SOM decomposer and mineral N (B&C) on 3*8 climatic year in two management situations (explained in subtitles).	59
Figure 39 : Schematic representation of the decomposition process in the Roth-C model (Coleman & Jenkinson, 2014).	62
Figure 40 : Selection of field experiments in AgroEcoSeqC.	64

Figure 41: Timeline of LTE Tillage and Cover Crop Management (Lithuania). Dark green: cover crop growing period (for cover crop sub-plots); Black striped: main crop growing period; Light green : intermediate period ; Tillage : tillage operations, except no-till treatment.	66
Figure 42: Timeline of LTE Clever Cover Cropping (The Netherlands). Dark green : cover crop growing period; Black striped: main crop growing period; light green : intermediate period.	67
Figure 43: Timeline of LTE Organic Matter (Belgium).	68
Figure 44 : Timeline of the New Experimental Field Fungi and Cover Cropping System (Turkey. Dark green : cover crop growing period; Black striped: main crop growing period.	69
Figure 45: Simulation of SOC; a) LTE Tillage, T1, T2, T3; b) LTE Clever Cover cropping, T1, T2, T3. Black dots denote treatments mean SOC;	71
Figure 46: continued; c) LTE Organic Matter, T1, T2, T3; d) NEF Fungi and Cover Crops, T1, T2, T3.	72

List of Tables

Table 1: Information about selected reviews of SOM and SOC models	15
Table 2: Summary of turnover times derived from modelling radiocarbon in SOM fractions for the boreal, temperate, and tropical forest soils. TT = Turnover Time. From Trumbore, 2000	16
Table 3 : Classification of SOM model compartmentation From Powlson et al. (2013)	21
Table 4 : Methods of SOC fractionation (see review of von Lützow et al. (2007) From Stockmann et al. (2013)	22
Table 5 : Four view of continuum decomposition chain which influence SOM compartmentation from Lehmann & Kleber (2015)	23
Table 6 : Representation of soil carbon in ecosystem models and recommendations for potential improvements. From Schimdt et Torn 2011.	34
Table 7 : Placing our modelling approach into current modelling work	35
Table 8 : 14 parameters of SYMPHONY model	39
Table 9: 31 parameters et ... variables d'états du modèle ModVege [ref Jouven] de l'analyse de sensibilité	41
Table 10 : Tested and done coupling work with toys models to integrate (1) SOM and SOC turnover (2) Microbial diversity (3) Plant biomass production and (4) Plant diversity	50
Table 11 : Carbon storage/destorage on 8*3 years on different management, with different values of parameters A. Mowing are realized on day 181, 237 and 303. Fertilization were realized on day 100, 200 and 250 with 50 N kg.ha-1 in order to compensate mowing effect	56
Table 12 : Carbon storage/destorage on 8*3 years on different management, with different values of parameters A. Mowing are realized on day 181, 237 and 303. Fertilization were realized on day 100, 200 and 250 with 50 N kg.ha-1 in order to compensate mowing effect	58
Table 13: Indicators with high correlation- and p-values with the optimal RMF.	73
Table 14 : Impact of RMF on SOC stocks after 20 years.	75

1 Introduction and methodology

The AGROECOSeqC project aims to evaluate the impact of agroecological management practices on agricultural systems, particularly focusing on key ecological processes such as plant diversification, microbial carbon use efficiency, and nutrient cycling. These practices influence the long-term storage of soil organic carbon (SOC) by enhancing soil structure, promoting carbon sequestration, and improving nutrient cycling. As a result, they contribute to critical ecosystem services such as increased soil fertility, water retention, and greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation. These processes are crucial to improve ecological functions, including increasing stable SOC pools, reducing N-leaching, mitigating GHG emissions, and increasing biomass production and crop yields.

The success of integrating ecological processes into agriculture practices can be measured through two main services: plant productivity and GHG mitigation (Figure 1). Plant productivity directly addresses the agricultural objective of feeding both animals and humans. GHG mitigation, on the other hand, is related to climate change and the associated loss of soil C and N from soil to the atmosphere. Human activities contribute to GHG emissions, which drive climate change, as highlighted in the IPCC reports. These two services encompass other related processes such as C storage, nutrient cycling, water storage, purification, and biodiversity conservation, all of which are interlinked by cause-and-effect relationships.

Figure 1 : Non-exhaustive examples of relationships and dependencies of factors and processes to our two main objectives of plant productivity (PP) and greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation. Colors refer to other work packages (WP) of the AGROECOSeqC project that will shape our work (see Figure 2). Anthropogenic activities are not placed on this graph because we consider it playing a role on every of those components.

Soil organic matter (SOM) and soil organic carbon (SOC) play key roles in delivering these services. SOM is the non-living organic matter component of soil at different decomposition stages which is consequently a heterogeneous mixture with a very diverse range of chemical and physical materials (Kumada, 1988). The decomposition of SOM influences nutrient availability, soil structure and the

global carbon cycle by contributing to CO₂ emissions. SOC, which refers to C derived from organic sources, forms a critical part of SOM and interacts with other elements (Stockmann et al., 2013). Soils with higher organic matter content tend to have better physical properties compared to soils with reduced organic matter (Powlson et al., 2013). Notably, soils contain more organic C than the global vegetation and atmosphere combined, meaning even small shifts in SOM decomposition can significantly affect atmospheric GHG concentrations (Schmidt et al., 2011).

SOM and SOC enter the soil system and undergo decomposition, either being released into the atmosphere or incorporated by living organisms. The long-term storage of SOC and SOM is determined by interactions between soil, plant, and atmospheric components across different time and spatial scales (Manlay et al., 2007; Manzoni & Porporato, 2009). To measure the effect of factors such as anthropic activities or climatic change on plant productivity and GHG mitigation, we set up experimentation and analyse result with statistical analysis. While data-driven models are powerful to generate hypothesis and identify causal links, they provide only a snapshot of a system at a given time, especially in soils, which are inherently opaque environments. To gain a more comprehensive understanding, mechanistic models are essential. These models attempt to capture the processes governing SOM and SOC turnover. Their level of development reflects the current state of knowledge about the system (e.g. “4 per 1000” initiative, INRAe). Mechanistic models serve two purposes: they integrate key processes based on research findings to simulate C flow and match observed data, and they highlight gaps in our understanding when the models fail to align with real-world data.

The objective of this deliverable is to quantify and understand changes in SOM and SOC dynamics in response to agroecological management practices, using some of these mechanistic models. Our work builds upon previous work packages (WPs) within the AGROECOSeqC project (Figure 2) to guide model development and selection.

Figure 2 : Mind map of other working packages of the AGROECOSeqC project that will frame our work.

The structure of this report is as follows:

- (1) A literature review of existing SOM and SOC models to establish the current state of knowledge.
- (2) Integration of new processes to improve the representation of SOC dynamics using simplified models.
- (3) Enhancement to classical models to improve accuracy and predictive power.

2 Review of soil organic matter and carbon models: Key considerations for model selection

2.1 Introduction

The concept of SOM and SOC have emerged and have been studied for different purpose and societal context across the time which has an impact on mechanist model design (Manlay et al., 2007). These lasts distinguish three periods in the scientific perception of SOM: “the humic period” (before 1840), the “mineralist period” (with the approximate dates of 1840–1940) and the “ecological period” from 1940 up to the present time. The first two periods are related to the evolution of plant nutrition theories and under a productivity purpose, while the third is characterized by the perception of SOM’s contribution to ecosystem function and human well-being under a multifunctionality purpose.

In order to catch the complexity of process affecting the SOM and SOC dynamics, we will use latter what we call mechanistic models. In the widest sense, a model is a symbolic representation of certain aspects of a real-world object or phenomenon (Pavé, 2012). We define a mechanistic model as a mathematical model which transpose mechanisms into equations. Early mathematical models described the processes of SOM decomposition and mineralization by using simple chemical and spatial models (Manzoni & Porporato, 2009; Ostle et al., 2009). If linear systems of ODEs with constant coefficients can be solved analytically, regardless of their compartmental organization, nonlinear models need to be solved numerically. In this sense, modelling evolves in line with advances in computing technologies and research.

This bibliography synthesis does not bring more information or hypothesis than those found in literature. Our objectives are to (1) review the state of the art of SOM and SOC modelling and open our mind view on this subject (2) to frame our work and place it into current models’ development and work package of AGROECOSeqC and (3) to select models we are going to work with. To do so, we will review previous work on SOM and SOC modelling and then we will organize our work into (1) a first part scaling our model choice, (2) a second part placing our work into researching flow and work packages of the AGROECOSeqC project and (3) a third part referring to reliability of models and their evolution.

2.2 Method

Studies on soil organic carbon really increase recently to find a solution to diverse problematics as erosion, fertility, loss of biodiversity, carbon storage. Review on modelling works has already been made up to answer different specific questions. We then naturally start our process of synthesis by looking at it (Table 1). In each of those reviews, we could find that models are classified into tables according to the question of authors (see Annex 1 for table).

Title of the review	Number of models reviewing	Date	Author
Evaluation of Soil Organic Matter Models: Using Existing Long-Term Datasets	7	1995	Powlson et al.
Modelling refractory soil organic matter	At least 33	2000	Falloon et al.
Soil carbon and nitrogen mineralization: Theory and models across scales	250	2009	Manzoni & Porporato
Integrating plant–soil interactions into global carbon cycle models	11	2009	Ostle et al.
Modelling soil carbon and nitrogen cycles during land use change	5	2011	Battle-Aguilar et la.
The knowns, known unknowns and unknowns of sequestration of soil organic carbon	At least 11	2013	Stockmann et al.
Current developments in soil organic matter modelling and the expansion of model applications: a review	At least 70	2015	Campbell & Paustian
Global patterns and controls of soil organic carbon dynamics as simulated by multiple terrestrial biosphere models: Current status and future directions	10	2015	Tian et al.
Soil C and N models that integrate microbial diversity	50	2016	Louis et al.
Microbial Models for Simulating Soil Carbon Dynamics	71	2023	Chandel et al.
Radiocarbon analysis reveals underestimation of soil organic carbon persistence in new-generation soil models	5 (to 15)	2023	Brunmayr et al.

By reading those reviews, different great topics appears in order to select the models we will use. Time and special scales are part of these selection factors and are related to questions and process we want to study.

2.2.1 Different scales of study

2.2.1.1 Time scale and carbon recalcitrance

The soil carbon storage, which is equals to the soil carbon input minus the soil carbon output as CO₂ release in the atmosphere, is a question of time scale because the effect of different process doesn't

take effect at the same speed (e.g. soil tillage vs. change of land use). The key of SOM and SOC turnover is the carbon persistence in the soil, i.e. the period of time organic carbon remains in the soil (

Figure 3). Carbon datation analysis reveal that some organic carbon are very old into the soil (Table 2).

Table 2: Summary of turnover times derived from modelling radiocarbon in SOM fractions for the boreal, temperate, and tropical forest soils. TT = Turnover Time. From Trumbore, 2000

Site and SOM fraction	C stock (g C/m ²)	TT† (yr)	Source of mean residence time (MRT)
Boreal			
Surface moss and detritus	5800	60	¹⁴ C and C accumulation since last fire; chronosequence
Humic layer	9400	1000–1500	¹⁴ C and C accumulation since deglaciation
Total to mineral (40 cm)	15 200	650–1250	
Temperate			
O leaves + roots	400	3–8	¹⁴ C of leaf and root detritus
O humics	1300	30–40	¹⁴ C and C accumulated since reforestation; CO ₂ fluxes
A/Ap low density roots	100	3–8	¹⁴ C of root detritus
A/Ap low density humics	2600	50–160	¹⁴ C of < 2 g/cm ³ fraction
A/Ap dense	600	160–400	¹⁴ C of > 2 g/cm ³ fraction
B1 low density	1200	800–1000	¹⁴ C of < 2 g/cm ³ fraction
Total to 40 cm	6200	200–310	
Tropical			
O leaves	325	<1	litter flux and layer inventory
A (0–40 cm) low density	830	1–3	¹⁴ C of < 2 g/cm ³ fraction
A dense hydrolyzable	3110	10–30	¹⁴ C and C removed hydrolysis
A dense nonhydrolyzable	1190	>6000	¹⁴ C of > 2 g/cm ³ residue
Total to 40 cm	5460	1040	

However, some effects due to changes in soil management or land use can appear very quickly. For example the introduction of a new crop could cause an immediate change in the microbial composition of the rhizosphere and so on CO₂ release in the atmosphere. Though, changes in the total quantity of carbon present in soil tend to occur slower (Parton, 1996). Powlson et al. (1987) gave examples of this from experiments in which spring barley straw was either burnt or incorporated into soil after harvest. Even though the quantity of straw incorporated was substantial, there was no statistically significant difference in the total SOC content between the two treatments 18 years after they started. This is explained by the fact that the initial SOC content was high and partly because spatial variability makes changes in any soil property difficult to measure. In models, it is essential to choose the time scale of the simulation (i.e. a month, a year, few multiple years, centuries) and so the integration time step (i.e. minutes, hours, /night cycle, days, months, season cycles, years) regarding the process we want to capture.

Figure 3: Molecular structure decomposition rate – This figure compiles data from surface horizons of 20 long-term field experiments (up to 23 years) in temperate climate, using ¹³C labelling to trace the residence time of bulk SOM and of individual molecular compounds. The variation in turnover time is also seen in the compounds of microbial origin analysed for ¹³C content, phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA) produced by Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria and amino sugars (hexosamines). For clarity, we have excluded outliers. Data points: thin horizontal lines, 10th and 90th percentiles; box, 25th and 75th percentiles; central vertical line, median. From Schmidt et Torn 2011

Figure 4: percentage of models with given spatial and temporal scales, along with the type II regression line between them (dot-dashed line; $R^2 = 0.45$, $P < 0.0001$). From Manzoni & Porporato 2009

Powlson et al. (2013), in their review of 10 SOM models proposed a categorization in three units time step : Hours, Months, and Centuries. Explaining that with 720 hours per month, the first and second division are separated by 2 orders of magnitude; and with 1200 months per century, the second two are separated by 3 orders of magnitude (see **Error! Reference source not found.**Figure 5).

Figure 5: Model classification of Powlson et al. (2013).

They also choose to not classified models into spatial units because time scale were correlated with spatial scale, which was also the observation of Manzoni & Porporato (2009)(Figure 4). From a broader time, perspective, from the pedogenesis, SOM accumulation is different in certain soil groups with differences in parent material, degree of weathering and mineral composition. Kögel-Knabner & Amelung (2021)have summarized the basic SOM storage processes that differ from one soil group to another, in order to present an initial overview of SOM formation in the world's different terrestrial soils. They conclude that the specific pedogenic environment must be considered when assessing SOM

storage potentials at global level, and therefore in future global C models. In order to represent this SOM with a very long turnover rate, the RothC model integrate an IOM compartment which represent a carbon pool that does not exchange matters with others.

This highly persistent carbon pool has mainly been described as a humic substance which is a very stable end product from decomposition by micro-organism (Manlay et al., 2007). But this concept of decomposition rate of the molecular structure of organic residues has been revised and is not sufficient to explain the very long residence time of organic carbon in the soil (Figure 3 & Table 2). The question posed by Schmidt et al. (2011) is why, when organic matter is thermodynamically unstable, does it persist in soils, sometimes for thousands of years? In conclusion, the time scale of the processes involved in SOM and SOC dynamics can vary greatly, from the history of SOC stock evolution over a long period to the rapid microbial response of respiration. Modelers need to clearly define the time scale they choose for their model, bearing in mind that time scale is closely linked to spatial scale.

2.2.1.2 Spatial scale

SOM and SOC dynamics occur at different spatial scale, from molecular to continent. The process of CO₂ fixation by photosynthesis takes place at the scale of the plant cell, and will affect carbon distribution and component allocation at organism level. Moreover, biomass deposition on the ground can be considered on a zonal scale, but the balance of CO₂ flows is sometimes measured and calculated on a national scale.

From the parent material (e.g. volcanic glasses for andosols or swelling and shrinking clays for vertosols) and history (tropical, subtropical climatic conditions or anthropogenic disturbances), different soil types emerge with different properties (Kögel-Knabner & Amelung 2021). These different soil types will be structured differently. Soil is a highly heterogeneous, three-dimensional environment, with disconnected pores filled with air and/or water, and disparate resources that can act as hotspots for microbial growth. Combined with the influence of plants and soil fauna (e.g. insects and earthworms), as well as changes in soil moisture and temperature, the soil environment is highly dynamic (Jansson & Hofmockel, 2020).

In modelling, many biogeochemical models use a discrete representation of soil layers (e.g. the CENTURY model from Parton (1996) often linked by water flow, which drives the advection of dissolved organic and inorganic compounds along the profile. (Figure 6) Lehmann & Kleber (2015)(Table 5). There is another point of view concerning the continuous decomposition chain of organic matter with, for example, the Q-soil model having a continuous quality variable q and a carbon density function (Figure 6) , which is in line with the recent proposal by Lehmann & Kleber (2015) (Table 5).

Figure 6: Conceptual diagram of the main interactions between soil substrates and organisms, as represented by global and continuous spatial representations. Gray and white boxes represent carbon and nitrogen compartments and fluxes respectively. The dotted lines in the SOM boxes (left) illustrate qualitatively how the substrate and decomposer variables are treated as a continuum in the Q-soil model (Ågren and Bosatta, 1996). From Manzoni & Porporato, 2009

Everyone agreed that there is a **vertical distribution** of elements and this determine chemical reaction in the soil. Cook et al. (2013) model aimed to examine processes that determine the depth of oxygen extinction in soils at a finite depth after the study of an acid sulphate soil were oxygen concentration went to 0 at a depth of about 1 m. Oxygen extinction determines the oxic/anoxic boundary in a soil profile. This model is a revision of their first model, because it was using semi-infinite bottom boundary condition considering that the oxygen concentration with depth went to zero as depth went to infinity and was then not able to calculate where the oxygen concentration might go to zero in the soil profile. This model also gives an example of the relation between data and models. The error of some old model is to only take the first 30 centimetres of soil but it is to fit with observed data.

Apart the vertical soil profile organizing a vision into layer, we can add a **horizontal soil** profile taking in account pore space, soil aggregation, bioturbation, space around roots or horizontal transport of nutrients. Aggregate will for example limit the accessibility of SOM and SOC for microbial community, limit oxygen diffusion, regulate water flow and determine nutrient adsorption and desorption (Six et al., 2004). 3D structured models are now developed to study pore space in soil such as the model of Monga et al. (2008) (Figure 7).

Figure 7 : Model of pore space from 3D tomography image with – **A**) Perspective views of the drained pore space at –20 cm water pressures. Top left is initially water saturated pore space, top right shows border balls drained and down shows equilibrium state. Grey balls are filled with air and white balls are filled with water and **B**) Conceptual diagram of the model From (Monga et al., 2008)

If we consider now not just the soil but a soil as a **part of a system**, process as erosion and landscape position as altitude in Altitude. Doetterl et al. (2016), in their review, synthesized erosion process including soil sub-layer exposure, lateral C flux, transport and deposition on bulk SOC. They relate some attempts to implement empiric relations between mean erosion/deposition rates and C enrichment with for example, the SPEROS-C (Quijano et al., 2017) (see Annex, **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 8 : . Overview on soil C cycling in dynamic landscapes and the key mechanisms involved in C sequestration and release from soils. Processes indicated at the plateau/summit position take place along the whole hillslope, but are affected by soil redistribution.

Figure 8 show the carbon distribution on a hillslope as an example of altitude effect on SOM and SOC (Gutiérrez-Girón et al., 2015). Finally, SOM and SOC dynamics are closely related to the system management and spatial dynamics depends on ecosystem type (Jansson & Hofmockel, 2020). In modelling vision itself, spatial scale can be treated as modular structure. Ellis et al. (2020) in a review dedicated to the synergy between mechanist modelling and data-driven models cite a publication of France (1988) described three important attributes of a “hierarchical” mechanist model :

1. Each level has its own language, concepts or principles. For example, the terms ‘forage DM’ and ‘pasture management’ have little meaning at the cell or organelle level;
2. Each level is an integration of items from lower levels. Discoveries or descriptions at a lower level can be used at the higher level in an explanatory way to aid understanding (mechanism and mode-of-action) and

3. Successful operation at the higher level requires the lower level to function properly but not necessarily vice versa. The example France (1988) provides is that of a cup – if it is smashed it will no longer function as a cup, but the molecular properties are hardly altered.

To conclude, spatial and temporal scale and we want to press the idea that model is design in a very precise context and system because it is aimed to be relevant regarding observed data. The question we can ask ourselves regarding spatial scale is about which homogeneous unit of soil we consider.

2.2.2 Important factor and process represented in models

In this part, we wanted to have an overview of construction, process and pools involved in SOM and SOC models analysed regarding our objectives. We include the construction of SOM and SOC models with compartmentation (all WP), the role of biotic part with microbial (related to WP2, 4 & 6), plants (WP2 & 5) and other soil fauna (WP3 & 5), the physicochemical protection and aggregate process in soil (WP6) but also the climate effect with water flux, frozen and fire event (all WP) and finally the synchrony and anthropic impact on SOM and SOC models (WP5).

2.2.2.1 SOM and SOC compartmentation pools (all WP)

The continuum decomposition state of SOM is usually discretised in models into pools of SOM, carbon or other elements (Stockmann et al., 2013). Powlson et al. (2013) in their classification recognize six categories of SOM compartmentation in models (Table 3). As an example, SOM pools are discretizing by size and turnover rate in Herfurth (2015) model with particulate organic matter (POM), aggregate organo-mineral (AOM) fraction and humified C. POM fractions has a faster turnover rate (less than 1–10 years) than AOM and humified C associated with mineral particles (10–1000 years).

Kinetic	Including the diversity of turnover rates. Kinetically homogeneous units may be biologically and chemically dissimilar but have similar accessibility in soil.
Biochemical	separations recognize the discrete chemical components of litter and to some degree SOM. They can be analytically separated and their dynamics measured unambiguously. It is however is valid only of the discrete chemicals behave independently in soil.
Biomass / Kinetic	A mixed system, because they include biomass as a unit of compartmentalization, but the biomass is defined on the basis of its turnover rate.
Functional/ Morphological	separations recognize a connection between the properties that define the biological function of a plant or microbial component (e.g. cell wall) and the properties governing its fate in soil. Recognition of litter layers was also considered to fit into this category.
Cohort	the system considering litter and SOM as a continuum and treat each addition of litter as a cohort that decomposes to progressively more stable products over time.
None	Finally, no compartmentalization may have been employed, in which case the designation was None.

But SOM compartmentation really depends on the historical vision of SOM material. Since the 1950s, the “humic substance” concept is challenged. Schmidt et al. (2011) and Stockmann et al. (2013), point out this ‘division’ originate from and led to historical methods of SOC fractionation (density fractionation, particle size fractionation, chemical extraction) (Figure 9 & Table 4). Those methods don’t fully incorporate concepts as stabilization on mineral surfaces or protection by aggregates.

Figure 9 : A, Based on chemical analysis of the extracted materials (Observed), the formation of humic polymers (Interpretation) was postulated to be an important source of recalcitrant SOM. B, Direct high-resolution *in situ* observations with non-destructive techniques (Observations) have been able to explain the functional group chemistry of the extracted humic substances as relatively simple biomolecules (Interpretation), without the need to invoke the presence of unexplainable. From Schmidt et al. (2011)

Table 4 : Methods of SOC fractionation (see review of von Lützow et al. (2007) From Stockmann et al. (2013))

Physical fractionation		Chemical fractionation
Aggregate size fractionation		Chemical extractions
Macroaggregates (>250 μm)/wet sieving/slaking/dispersion (ultrasonic)	DOC (dissolved organic matter)/less than 0.45 μm in solution	Used to separate ‘humic substances’ into humic acids, fulvic acids and humin/ based on solubility in alkali and acid solutions, the most common are NaOH and Na ₄ P ₂ O ₇ and Microbial biomass C/i.e. chloroform used as fumigant
Density fractionation		Hydrolysis
Heavy fraction (organo-mineral complexes), Light fraction, POM (particulate organic matter)	Separated using liquids with a certain density (between 1.6 and 2.0 g cm ⁻³)	Used to separate hydrolytic bonding of carbohydrates/protein molecules, etc./for instance HF to separate mineral-OM associations/or HCl to quantify proportion of SOC association with proteins, amino acids, amino sugars
Particle size fractionation		Oxidation
Clay-sized, silt-sized and sand-sized particles		Used to remove labile/active fraction of SOM (i.e. plant residues)/most common agents are H ₂ O ₂ , NaOCl and KMnO ₄

Lehmann & Kleber (2015) attempt to assemble current knowledge and propose a new compartmentation method in models and try to put an ending to the “humic substance” concept (Table 5). The persistence of organic matter in soils is now considered to be an emergent property derived from biological processes and the physico-chemical boundary conditions of the surrounding soil environment (e.g., parent material, soil depth, climate) rather than being dependent on the intrinsic chemical properties of SOM itself (Vogel et al., 2024)

In recent advances, the emerging point of view is that carbon stability in soil mainly depends on its biotic and abiotic environment and is an ecosystem property (Schmidt et al., 2011). However, today's already tested models rely on this idea of organic material pool and some of them presents good result

in their frames of use. Finally, the type of SOM compartmentation chosen is related to the homogenous spatial unit in the model and to process we want to capture.

Table 5 : Four view of continuum decomposition chain which influence SOM compartmentation from Lehmann & Kleber (2015)

The 'humification' model	The 'Selective preservation'	The "Progressive decomposition"	The proposed soil continuum model (SCM)
<p>Transformation or synthesis of the initial decomposition products into large, dark-coloured compounds. The resulting macromolecules is resistant to decomposition and consequently, older than the rest of the soil organic matter. Given the lack of a universally accepted definition of 'humic substances' across disciplines and the lack of evidence for their physical existence independent of the alkaline extraction procedure, there is no agreement on this process.</p>	<p>Organic inputs are composed of both labile and relatively recalcitrant compounds, the latter being used by microorganisms only when the former are exhausted. However, there is now robust evidence that, under suitable conditions, decomposer organisms have the ability to decompose even presumably persistent materials. Even lignin decomposition is fastest at the early stages of decomposition, as long as it is easily accessible and small organic molecules are available as a source of energy to help mineralize the lignin.</p>	<p>Soil organic matter consists of a range of organic fragments and microbial products of all sizes at various stages of decomposition. Throughout this process, these materials remain on an energetic downhill trajectory, as opposed to the hypothetical 'humic substances.</p>	<p>A continuum of organic fragments is continuously processed by the decomposer community from large plant and animal residues towards smaller molecular size. At the same time, greater oxidation of the organic materials increases solubility in water as well as the opportunity for protection against further decomposition through greater reactivity towards mineral surfaces and incorporation into aggregates.</p>

2.2.2.2 Microbial activity and diversity (WP2, WP4, WP6)

Dynamics of soil C in soil is greatly driven by soil microorganisms which group together soil fungi and bacteria mainly (Louis et al., 2016). Chandel et al. (2023) reviewed 71 soil models integrating a microbial part revealing four main microbial processes incorporated into SOC models: (1) microbial-mediated decomposition, (2) mineral interaction, (3) microbial necromass recycling, and (4) active and dormant microbial dynamics (Figure 10). 61 models consider microbial biomass as a decomposer of SOC and the remaining 10 models, although they simulate a distinct microbial biomass pool, consider it as a substrate pool, usually as a carbon pool. In their review work, they highlighted that microbial

biomass has been considering in models after recent advances in microbiology and genomics such as extracellular enzyme or that under natural environmental conditions. Especially the fact that soil bacteria exist in three physiological states: dead, alive, and dormant.

Figure 10 : Historic development of microbial models since 1975 (a) and (b) and percentage of microbial models with consideration of major microbial process (c). The percentage was calculated as the number of models considering each process divided by the total number of published models in each time period. From Louis et al. 2016 publication mineralization and immobilization; SIMP, simplified mineralization formulations (from Manzoni & Porporato, 2009)

A way to integrate microbial effect on SOM with a single microbial pool is the use of a single parameter named Carbon use efficiency (CUE). CUE is the efficiency of the catabolism of detrital organic matter conversion into microbial biomass. It controls the conversion of plant-produced carbon into microbial products, rates of ecosystem carbon storage, and energy and material flow to higher trophic levels (Sinsabaugh et al., 2013). But as soil microorganisms carry out the dichotomous roles of mineralization of SOC and stabilization of carbon inputs into organic forms, the representation of functional groups of microorganism in models is important to deal with carbon and nitrogen cycle (Jansson & Hofmockel, 2020). New developments in molecular biology methods provided evidence that not only microbial abundance but also microbial diversity affects C and N cycling in the soil in different experimental and agricultural contexts (Baumann et al., 2013; Juarez et al., 2013).

Louis et al. (2016) reviewed 50 soil models integrating this microbial diversity. They explain that this diversity has long been assumed to have no functional significance because of the high functional redundancy of soil microorganisms. Several distinct microbial species can perform a similar reaction but being limited by different components (Vogel et al., 2024). But this assumption was partly justified by the lack of a demonstrated diversity function relationship, which was mainly attributed to technical limitations. Progress in analytical methods over the two last decades has generated new methods and has provided the necessary tools to reconsider this assumption (Maron et al., 2007).

We can distinguish two main type of diversity: taxonomic diversity (TD) and Functional diversity. The latter is a diversity with grouped microbial unit regarding a function related to substrate decomposition

kinetics, or a considering process (i.e denitrification, mineralization, enzyme secretion). As example, the ecosys model from Grant (1998), with 9 functional groups was made to estimate CH₄ emissions from wetlands and agricultural land. Methane is a terminal product of anaerobic respiration in saturated soils and a substrate of aerobic respiration in unsaturated soils (Figure 11 & Box 1). In FD, fungi and bacteria are usually grouped with no distinction if they have the same function. TD models may focus more on interactions along the food web. They are used to analyse contributions of these groups, specifically on N mineralisation or C and N dynamics. The microbial groups differ in their nutrient ratios, feeding preferences, life spans, assimilation efficiencies, production-to-assimilation ratios and decomposability. An example is the BACKWAVE model from Zelenev et al. (2006) aimed to study the regular oscillations in bacterial populations and growth rates of bacterial feeding nematodes (BFN) observations that occur after addition of fresh organic matter to soil (Figure 12). This model does not include fungi group with bacteria into a global microbial pool and consider a protozoa group. However, for bacteria, taxonomic classification is hard because of their asexual division and their horizontal genetic material transfer which make the barrier with functional groups very thin (Vandamme 2011).

Figure 11 : Flow diagram of ecosys model showing C transformations in a single substrate-microbe complex from Grant 1998. It is identified as a Functional Diversity model with 9 functional pools in Louis et al. (2016).

Box 1 : Short resume of ecosys chemical reactions - Acetate is transformed into CH₄ and CO₂ by Acetotrophic methanogens. Dihydrogen and CO₂ are transformed into CH₄ by Hydrogenotrophic methanogens. There is a community of Anaerobic acetogens producing Acetate and Heterotrophs groups (Denitrifying Heterotrophs and Aerobic Heterotrophs) producing CO₂. After, CH₄ can be transferred directly to the atmosphere or may move upwards into unsaturated soils and oxidized into CO₂ by autotrophic methanotrophs.

Figure 12 : Relational diagram of the carbon flow ($\mu\text{g C cm}^{-3}$) of the BACKWAVE model. With A_CO₂ : cumulative CO₂ sink to atmosphere ; BACT : total number of bacteria ; BFN : bacterial feeding nematodes ; COP : copiotrophic bacteria ; E : Enzymes ; HB : hydrolytic bacteria ; HUMOM : humus organic matter of soil ; LIRES : lignin fraction of plant residues ; OLIG : oligotrophic bacteria ; PRTZ : protozoa ; S : soluble substrate ; SOLOM : soluble organic matter of soil ; SORES : soluble plant residue ; STRES : stable fraction of plant residues ; STROM : structural organic matter of soil. Rectangles represent state variables, ovals—auxiliary variables, full lines—flows of matter (C or N), and dashed lines—flows of information. Flows of information ending in flows of matter indicate that the matter flow is influenced by the information flow. From Zelenev et al. (2006)

In SOM and SOC turnover models, microbial pools are usually decomposer pools (fungi and bacteria). However, the effect of mycorrhizal network has been recently more studied and it might have a strong effect to shape plant growth and relation between decomposers, SOM and SOC. Treseder (2016) and

Simard et al. (2012) explore possible exchanges between plant and mycorrhizal network and the MyScan model integrate it. The structural role of micro-organism is also poorly integrated in SOM and SOC models. Fungal mycelium can entangle particles within the hyphae network and cements them through extracellular polysaccharide production (Si et al. 2004). Another lack in models is the ecosystem regulation and biological controls of micro-organisms (Vogel, 2024)

2.2.2.3 Plant activity and diversity (WP2)

Plant in agricultural-systems are an important part of organic input but also an actor of his decomposition through microbial stimulation induced by exudation or competition with microbial pools for nutrients. Plant biomass production in SOM and SOC models is usually keep simple and has a function of representing the organic input into the soil (Manzoni & Porporato, 2009; Van Oijen et al., 2020). Plant are present in 20% models of Manzoni and Porporato, but most of them represent only the growth and death dynamic and sometimes a single mean plant with above and below-ground dynamic. In the other hands, soil is a simple part in physiological plant model.

Figure 13 : Percentage of biogeochemical models in different model classes. M: Soil microbiology, soil aggregate, and rhizosphere models; L: Litter decomposition model; S: Soil model with no dynamic vegetation components; E: Coupled soil-plant dynamic model; G: Coupled soil-plant-atmosphere model for global applications.

Some SOM and SOC models will focus on a special function of plants. Roose & Schnepf (2008) took stock of plant-soil interactions with a focus on roots. To a single root interacting with nutrients and water flows from a complex root system including exudates and root three-dimensional simulation. They highlighted the fact that mathematical nutrient and water flow studies through roots are not implemented enough in soil-plant models. In global crop plant-soil model root growth is often described as the root length density without the details of the root branching structure, and root water and solute uptake is generally described with some kind of approximation with regard to the concentration at the root surface. Rhizodeposition is generally ignored or treated as a separate soil organic matter pool. In fact, roots are the interface for exchanges between plant and soil. It also affects soil structure grouped into 5 categories: (1) root penetration, (2) changed soil water regime, (3) root exudation, (4) dead root decomposition and (5) root entanglement. (Six et al 2004)

Other models aimed to calculate GHG emission from crops or grassland take both part into account with plant physiology and soil model, this is the case of PaSim that modeled a mean grassland community with photosynthesis, growth of root and shoot, 4 age of plant organ and with a soil module inspired of CENTURY with 6 soil layers (Riedo et al., 1998). We can also cite as APSIM, Ceres and STICS trying to assemble a soil model with a physiological plant model (Gabrielle et al., 2006; Li et al., 2011). But those models simulate a mean community or a single species and do not simulate a diversity of plants.

As for microbial pool, we can distinguish two type of plant diversity: the functional diversity and the taxonomic diversity. Taxonomic diversity is used in crop models with a few species because species are usually well known. Ostle et al. (2009) reviewed dynamic global vegetation models (DGVMs) in which plant functional traits (PFTs) are used to describe functional diversity of plants, but they are usually kept into small groups with no really interactions between them. Some attempt has been proposed, we can cite an example with the DYNAGRAM (based on ModVege) which represent the competition between plants for resources of nutrients and light but with a very simplified soil only representing only the nitrogen pool and is more a vegetation model than a biogeochemical model (Moulin et al., 2021).

Plant diversity model are based on ecological theory managing community assembly as the competition for resource theory from Tilman (Miller et al., 2005) with one of its most assumption is that species that can survive at the lowest levels of a limiting resource will be the best competitor for that resource, or the filter theory of ecosystem telling that species can live in an ecosystem if they succeed to pass several conditions (Figure 14).

Figure 14 : Main processes or filters that structure a plant community. From Lortie et al. 2004.

But integrate this plant diversity in SOM and SOC models depends on the effect we want to capture about diversity. Do we want to model the population change, the succession of plants over time (stochastic process, seed dispersion, phenological process)? Do we want to modelized the different function of plant in the ecosystem (i.e. symbiosis N fixation, exudation, soil-engineering role of root, water utilization...)? Do we want to modelized interaction between plants (competition, facilitation,

defences information)? Or do we only represent a better organic matter deposition as an input in the soil model by modeled different material input over time and space?

To simulate plant diversity, some models can be implemented as a brick without modifying the original single plant model, this is the purpose of the CoSMo model which manage a plant diversity with suitability factors (Pisneddu et al., 2022) and the concept of a general growth model applicable to all plant types. While each species has very specific characteristics in the way it uses nutrients or develops certain organs, certain major physiological processes are similar for all. Photosynthesis, for example, is the transformation of solar energy into carbohydrates. We will be able to determine common processes according to the taxonomic proximity of the plants or the functional type of the plant (C3, C4, CAM) (Figure 15)

Figure 15 : Scale of similarities between plant groups, from simplest to most complex. Models can be developed for each level. From Wang, E., Robertson 2002.

The next challenge for models is to capture feedback of plants having an effect on SOM and SOC turnover and soil having an effect on plants diversity (Bloor & Bardgett, 2011).

2.2.2.4 Meso- macro-fauna activity and diversity (WP3)

Despite it was identify early as a key in SOM and SOC dynamic (Swift et al., 1979), meso and macro fauna are missing in mathematical mechanist models (Grandy et al., 2016). We did not find a review on this subject and literature cite few models and recent models such as KeyLink (Deckmyn et al., 2020), Romul_Hum (Komarov et al., 2017) including earthworm or bacteria and fungi predator, the BACKWAVE model (Zelenev et al., 2006)studying predator relations (Figure 12), SoMuChFood (Quévreux et al., 2024) with a multi-channel food web. Instead, some works argue about the importance of including this soil fauna in models and how doing it (Filser et al., 2016; Schmidt et al., 2011) and Grandy et al. (2016) ask themselves in the title of their article “Beyond microbes: Are fauna the next frontier in soil biogeochemical models?” (Figure 16).

Angst et al. conceptualized in a review the effect on SOM and SOC formation by (1) altering the quantity, quality, and location of organic matter in the soil via bioturbation and transformation

processes, (2) altering microbial biomass and community composition via active and/or indirect grazing on bacteria and fungi, (3) generating dissolved organic matter via processing of litter and other organic matter, and (4) influencing soil texture (and mineralogy) resulting in three main process : transformation, translocation and grazing (Figure 17). They found out that earthworm effect was the most studying process and indeed, in models we identify mostly the presence of earthworm integration and predators' relations.

Figure 16 : Main animal-mediated processes (boxes) affecting the eight insights (symbols) identified by Schmidt et al. (2011) that should be considered for improving SOM models. From Filser et al. 2016

Figure 17 : A resume of Soil fauna affecting formation pathways of POM and MAOM via transformation, translocation, and grazing. soil fauna effect. From Angst 2024.

As for plant diversity and microbial diversity, we might expect to find taxonomic diversity and functional diversity. Indeed, there are functional groups, functions related to bioturbation, functions of changing the colocation of microbial and SOM, or predation relations in cited models. But the most diversity proxy is the taxonomic diversity in soil food web model with taxonomic groups such as earthworm or termites (Vogel et al., 2024). There is a gap to cross between knowledge on soil fauna that are very species specialized and their integration into SOM and SOC models.

2.2.2.5 Nitrogen, other nutrient cycles and chemical elements (WP5)

Nitrogen cycle is tightly coupled with carbon cycle because N limitation is not rare in ecosystems and organisms demand often exceeds the rate of N supply (Ostle et al., 2009; Raven et al., 2004; Withers & Sylvester-Bradley, 1999). The growth rate of plant and then, the quality and quantity of SOM returning to the soil is depending on nitrogen cycle. But model of SOM and SOC does not always take nitrogen in account and according to Manzoni & Porporato (2009), it is varying with spatial and temporal scale (Figure 18).

Figure 18 : Percentages of models using the different N-limitation schemes (NLIM) at different spatial (e) and temporal (f) scales, including C-only (CM); no N-limitation (ND); inhibition factor (INH); Carbon losses in response to N-limitation (CO) and variable microbial or substrate C/N (CN). From Manzoni & Porporato (2009).

In SOM and SOC models, nitrogen sources can come from an input of organic matter pool with a define C/N as in NCSOIL (Powlson et al., 2013). A plant can be implemented in the model from a single plant with a N intake and a death rate dynamic as in SYMPHONY (Perveen et al., 2014) to a more complex plant with functional traits (PFTs) and interaction as in LPJ (Sitch et al., 2003). Nitrogen can come from an anthropic management fertilisation as in DRAINMOD-N II (M. A. Youssef et al., 2005) or atmospheric deposition and can be modified by tillage practice. The losses are usually N leaching, it can be simple rate as in ORCHIMICS 2.0, emission of gas as in TOUGHREACT-N (Maggi et al., 2008) (Figure 19). Or even by atmospheric erosion with a loss of SOM as in a modified version of CENTURY (Gregorich et al., 1998).

Figure 19: Schematic representation of the chain of biochemical nitrification and denitrification reactions (left side) and microbial respirations (right side). Mineral, liquid, and gaseous domains are separated by dashed lines. AOB, NOB, DEN, and AER stand for ammonia oxidizing bacteria, nitrite oxidizing bacteria, denitrifying bacteria, and aerobic bacteria, respectively. From Maggi et al. 2008

In models, Nitrogen is an element limiting process. In their reviewed work, (Manzoni & Porporato (2009), highlighted two schemes of mineralization/immobilization. The first scheme is based on the Mineralization–Immobilization Turnover (MIT) hypothesis, assumes that the organic N is transferred to the mineral pool before assimilation by microbes. Therefore, the only N assimilation pathway available is from the mineral pool. The second scheme assumes the existence of some direct (DIR) assimilation of organic N in low weight compounds, namely amino-acids, the N surplus of which is released in mineral form. All available organic N is directly assimilated prior to mineralization. At the micro-scale the MIT pathway is not realistic but it may be reasonable at the soil-core scale, where the

heterogeneous distribution of N-rich and N-poor substrates may drive strong N recycling. In real cases, however, a combination of the DIR and MIT pathways is typically observed at the macroscopic level, justifying the adoption of models that employ either one or the other pathway depending on the decomposer group (MIX), or the more flexible Parallel scheme (PAR) bridging DIR and MIT by using an organic nitrogen assimilation efficiency that may take any value between MIT and DIR.

Figure 20 : Historic trends of the percentages of models using different mineralization pathways (MIN). DIR, MIT and PAR: direct, mineralization-immobilization turnover, and parallel schemes, respectively; MIX, other schemes with simultaneous

Figure 21 : Historic trends of the percentages of models using the different N-limitation schemes (NLIM), including C-only models (CM). IND, no N-limitation; INH, inhibition factor; CO, carbon losses in response to N-limitation; CN+MIX, multiple formulations are simultaneously used.

One property of this limiting effect is the determination of carbon allocation between SOM and SOC pool. It can induce a competition between microbial pools and plant pool. And the integration of a biological N fixation strategy among plant will change SOM and SOC dynamic as implemented in MOMOS model or PaSim model (Pansu et al., 2018; Riedo et al., 1998). Even if the N supplied to the plant through mycorrhizal symbioses in exchange for plant C is not well represented in model, despite the evident importance of this interaction (Allen & Allen, 2017; Ostle et al., 2009; Smith & Smith, 2011). An attempted has been proposed with the MysCaN model (Orwin et al., 2011). A good overview of N pool and process are represented on Figure 22 from Ostle et al. (2009).

Figure 22 : (a) ECOSSE ecosystem soil N model structure showing integration of plant-soil N cycle with multi-pool soil organic matter model and, (b) the Fixation and Uptake of Nitrogen (FUN) model flowchart with four pathways of plant N uptake (passive uptake, active uptake, biological N fixation and re-translocation). From Oslte 2009

There is considerable evidence that other limiting nutrients including phosphorous (P) or potassium (K) have an important regulatory function in terrestrial ecosystems (Sardans et al., 2023; Wardle et al., 2009). In the Q-model_v4.0 and CENTURY integrate phosphorus (Bosatta & Ågren, 1985; Parton, 1996), which predominating abiotic controls, such as mineral composition, soil pH and redox status (Vogel et al., 2024).

2.2.2.6 Soil structure, Aggregates and physical/chemical protection (WP6)

The idea of only the chemical composition of SOM to explain recalcitrant carbon has been challenged because study show molecules that were supposed to decompose slowly (e.g. lignin, nitrogen gradient, lipids) can decompose fast under special condition (Schmidt et al., 2011). Indeed, biological (i.e plants, micro-organism, meso- and macro-fauna) and physicochemical influences from the surrounding environment reduce the probability and the rate of decomposition and allow the SOM and SOC to persist. Soil is a structured 3D environment were chemical element interact with each other. There are two physico-chemical protection scales: (1) the adsorption/ desorption on mineral surfaces and (2) the aggregation process.

In a lot of soil types, clay fraction represents the main reactive mineral surface for the stabilization of microbial residues (Kögel-Knabner & Amelung, 2021). Stewart et al. (2007) propose the 'soil carbon saturation concept' and confirmed in experiments that a soil's capacity to retain microbial residues in a stabilized Mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) pool has an upper limit mainly constrained by a soil's physicochemical characteristics related to clay content and mineralogy (e.g. content of Al and Fe oxides) Vogel et al. (2024). However, the limited capacity of soil for MOAM depending on soil texture was recently questioned by Schweizer (2022). Using various chemical imaging techniques, he showed that the distribution of MOAM is patchy and piled up at a minor part of mineral surfaces rather than covering them homogeneously. Thus, the capacity of C sequestration appears decoupled from the extension of mineral surfaces Vogel et al. (2024).

This led to the second process of aggregation. SOM is going to interact with mineral element and will form structural unit call aggregate that will protect them from being degraded. Six et al. 2004 reviewed aggregate process along an historical view and put forward the aggregate hierarchy concept where it is postulated that there are different binding agents (i.e. transient versus temporary versus persistent binding agents) acting at different hierarchical stages of aggregation. Those binding agents can be oxides, calcium or even microbial and root product. We distinguish macro-aggregate and micro-aggregate. Mycelium is a part of macroaggregate formation (Si et al. 2004) and the mucilage of bacteria and fungi enhance the microaggregate. Those aggregate prevent SOM and SOC from low predation, accessibility, protection against toxic materiel. Aggregation is linked with porosity because smaller

aggregates include smaller pores and will be more stable because there will be a lower accessibility for microorganisms and enzymes, also resulting in a slowed down P turnover (Siebers et al. 2018, Vogel et al.2024).

Figure 23: A time line of the critical advancement in the understanding of soil organic matter-aggregation interactions. From Six et al 2004

Meurer et al. (2020b) interest himself at porosity, within a dual porosity framework, changes in SOM alters the total porosity and pore size distribution. In this model, soil structure affects SOM stabilization via slower mineralization rates for SOM stored in the microporous region.

Several factors influence soil aggregation: (1) soil fauna; (2) soil microorganisms; (3) roots; (4) inorganic binding agents; and (5) environmental variables (Six et al., 2004) And aggregation could be an important factor of SOM and SOC stabilization but its integration in models is still in front of us (Table 6).

Table 6 : Representation of soil carbon in ecosystem models and recommendations for potential improvements. From Schmidt et Torn 2011.

Insight	Properties of most published models	Recommendations
1. Molecular structure	Decay rate of all pools keyed to substrate (or texture in CENTURY-type models*) and modified by moisture and temperature as constant Q_{10} above 0 °C.	Model decay rate as function of substrate properties and positions in microenvironment, microbial activity, and soil conditions including pH, temperature and moisture. See 4, 5, 6, 8.
2. Humic substances	Have a cascade of increasing intrinsic recalcitrance due to decomposition and synthesis.	Replace the cascade with cycling of organic matter into and out of microbial biomass. See 1, 8.
3. Fire-derived carbon	Do not include fire-residues as inputs or SOM. Do not represent decay of analogous substrates.	Add input pathway for fire-derived carbon. Add aromatic compounds to SOM types.
4. Roots	Parameterize litter quality with leaf/needle chemistry. Have simplified root and dissolved organic carbon inputs.	Use separate characterizations for below-ground and above-ground inputs. See 6.
5. Physical heterogeneity	Lack physical processes, such as aggregation (some have tillage factor), spatial heterogeneity, or processes that would produce priming effect†.	Non-normal probability distributions, density-dependent terms for organic matter and microbial biomass. Parameters from 3D, fine-resolution models.
6. Soil depth	No change in processes or rate constants with depth of soil or carbon input. Site-level tuning required to reproduce long turnover times.	Representations of mineral associations, root and dissolved organic inputs, and physical disconnections. Explicit depth resolution for decomposition and transport.
7. Permafrost	Lack processes governing permafrost soil carbon cycling. Lack fully coupled methane biogeochemistry.	Add O ₂ limitation and freezing effects on CO ₂ and CH ₄ production. Develop soil columns to represent inundation, permafrost thaw and thermokarst.
8. Soil micro-organisms	Treat microbial biomass as pool of active carbon. Lack effects of microbial community or enzymes on rates and decomposition products.	Create and model microbial functional types, analogous to plant functional types. Introduce full soil nitrogen cycle coupled to carbon cycle.

This idea that SOM and SOC stability does not result in an intrinsic property but it is more a matter of accessibility is an emerging concept and the title of an article “Soil organic matter turnover is governed by accessibility not recalcitrance” from Dungait et al 2012 (Figure 24)

Figure 24 : A synopsis of eight insights, contrasting historical and emerging views of soil carbon cycling. The historical view (a) has emphasized above-ground plant carbon inputs and organic matter in the top 30 cm of soil. Stable organic matter is seen to comprise mainly selectively preserved plant inputs and de novo synthesis products like humic substances, whose chemical complexity and composition render them nearly inert relative to microbial degradation. The emerging understanding (b) is that the molecular structure of organic material does not necessarily determine its stability in soil (1; molecular structure). Rather, SOM cycling is governed by multiple processes (5) shaped by environmental conditions (such as physical heterogeneity). Plant roots and rhizosphere inputs (4; roots) make a large contribution to SOM, which is mainly partial degradation and microbial products and fire residues (3) rather than humic substances (2). The vulnerability of deep soil carbon (6; deep carbon) to microbial degradation (8; soil micro-organisms) in a changing environment, such as thawing permafrost (7; thawing permafrost) remains a key uncertainty. From Schmidt et Torn 2011

2.3 Discussion and Conclusion

We argue that the persistence of SOC in soil is due to complex interactions between SOM and its environment, such as the interdependence of compound chemistry, reactive mineral surfaces, climate,

water availability, soil acidity, the presence of potential degraders in the immediate microenvironment and of other fauna that move material or transform it. The model capable of taking all these processes into account, individualizing their effects to reveal the system's emergent properties, does not yet exist. There are still many stages to go through, firstly in terms of experimentation and statistical analysis of the data, and secondly in terms of the models, adding the missing elements step by step and using the knowledge acquired. However, our approach has enabled us to situate ourselves and select the models we'll be working on to take this work forward.

Exploring new modelling solutions

Based on the results of the previous WP, we will produce new simple “toy models” in order to investigate how soil biome and its interaction with plant roots can be integrated to classical models to represent soil organic matter dynamic. This approach was already used for studying how priming effect and microbial diversity influence soil/plant interactions and ecosystem C and nitrogen (N) dynamics by Perveen et al., 2014, with the model SYMPHONY. For all of these toy models, we will produce an analytical study (steady state, stability) and some quantitative indicators. This, coupled with the results of the multivariate data analysis done in the task 7.1, will allow to determine which process is important and how we can implement it in order to model SOM dynamics. The results of this task will feed subtask => grassland, semi-natural system

Improving classical models

The RothC model is widely used in EU Member States and the EU level, e.g. Nutri2Cycle (Lesschen et al., 2019). This model recognises 5 SOC pools of which the BIO pool represents carbon stored in the microbial biomass. Not only have pool size and turnover rate of the BIO pool been poorly validated, but the concept falls short in taking soil biodiversity into account. Furthermore, the model may be extended to include C from plant roots. Based on the outcomes of Tasks 7.1 and 7.2.1., the inclusion of the effect of the soil biome may be improved and eventually including interaction with plant roots. To this end, several adaptations of the RothC model will be tested with data from selected LTEs and evaluation made relative to time series of measured SOC from selected LTEs reserved for validation.

3 Integrating new process to improve SOC dynamics representation by using simple models

3.1 Introduction

We wanted to study plant diversity effect on SOM and SOC dynamics. Positive links are made between carbon storage, productivity and biodiversity (Conant et al., 2017; Gross et al., 2009).). But these relationships also depend on pedoclimatic conditions, management and the functions of plants present in the community, such as legumes. (Loreau et al., 2001; Rajaniemi, 2003).

To understand those complex relations, we created a model integrating (1) SOM and SOC turnover (2) Microbial mineralization/immobilization (3) Plant biomass production and (4) Plant diversity in the case of a permanent grassland with mowing and fertilisation management. We implemented nitrogen fixation as a plant function in our system. We wanted to have a model simple enough to be manipulated and modify easily but a model including enough information to be tested against data and be relevant. This model is going to be a basis for further questions. To do so, we have coupled simple models already tested and approved to fulfilled our 4 objectives.

3.2 Method

3.2.1 Modeling framework and bank of mechanistic models

With these objectives in mind, a literature review highlighted a number of interesting models. We frame our work on a typical Massif Central permanent grassland with mowing and fertilization, but no grazing. This dimension adds a new complexity with the management of the animal subsystem, spatial heterogeneity due to animal preferences, etc. Our models are therefore based on the scale of a homogeneous plot, with a daily time step. We have selected models from literature and we coupled them to create a final model. Our future idea is to implement them into a model bank in order to manipulate them easily and separately but also to add some function in those models and to coupled them with a modular approach. We used the R language with R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt) with the deSolve, readsdr, tictoc, ggplot2, dplyr and basic R studio packages. This model bank will be located first on a private INRAe gitlab, which is intended to be freely licensed. Two models have been selected

as the basis for our work, the first one is ModVege, a biomass production model already tested and validated against observation (Jouven, Carrere and Baumont, 2006a; Calanca et al., 2016) at UREP. And the second is the SYMPHONY model, that provide a carbon cycle evaluation with a vision of mineralizer/ immobilizer functional microbial groups including the nitrogen dynamics (Perveen et al., 2014). In a first step to introduce plant diversity, we interest ourself into legume/grass functional group. Finally, we choose two way of plant interaction in our model with Cosmo and DYNAGRAM based on different ecological theory of plant co-existence in an environment.

3.2.2 Meteo data

ModVege has following forcing variables: photosynthetically active radiation (PARI), temperature (T), precipitations (PP) and potential evapotranspiration (PET). We retrieved data at same year and same places (Marcenat station 15190 FRANCE, 1993 - 2000) on CLIMATIK platform. This data has been recently free-licenced published.

However, in CLIMATIK' data, on 2922 days, they were 14% of missing values for PET and 1% for global radiation (RG). We gap-filled those values with simple linear models according to the relation between PET, RG and T. Linear models (eq.1) and (eq.2) were made on brut data and (eq.3) was made with gap-filled datas. Gap-filling linear models gave us negatives values near to zero for PET, so we replace them with zeros.

Gap-filling of PET with RG and Temperature to gap 418 data: R-squared = 0.9

$$PET = -0.1128 + 8.798 \times 10^{-4} \times RG + 2.867 \times 10^{-2} \times TM + 4.920 \times 10^{-5} \times RG \times TM \quad (1)$$

Gap-filling of PET avec Temperature to gap 31 data: R-squared = 0.6

$$PET = -0.438717 + 0.196121 \times TM \quad (2)$$

Gap-filling of RG avec PET to gap 31 data: R-squared = 0.8

$$RG = 385.273 + 478.955 \times PET \quad (3)$$

In those climatic data, we had the global radiation (RG J/m²) but ModVege use the PARI. We calculated PARI from RG (eq.) (Jacovides et al., 2003).

$$PAR = 0.48 \times \frac{RG}{100} \quad (4)$$

Data from the publication and data founded on the CLIMATIK platform (Fig 1a, Fig 1b) has similar means but there are not exactly same data. There is globally more variation of temperature in our data with bigger standard deviation and a strong difference between September and October for the precipitation.

Figure 25, A: Climatic data from Jouven et al. (2006) on Marcenat INRAe research station, Auvergne, altitude 1100 m a.s.l) : mean daily temperature (solid line) and monthly precipitation(bars) with their standard deviation, on 8 years (1993-2000).

Figure 25, B: Climatic data from CLIMATIK platform on Marcenat INRAe research station, Auvergne : mean daily temperature (solid line) and monthly precipitation(bars) with their standard deviation, on 8 years (1993-2000).

3.2.3 SYMPHONY, a microbial-driven SOM model.

SYMPHONY is a theoretical model that studies the priming effect. This effect corresponds to a change in the rate of mineralization of soil organic matter (SOM) by microorganisms resulting from an input of fresh organic matter (FOM) (Perveen et al., 2014). When FOM is added, micro-organisms are stimulated by the provision of energy that is easy to break down and use. Respiration of these micro-organisms increases. The study of this phenomenon is important for the control of CO₂ emission and carbon storage as microorganisms carry out the dichotomous roles of mineralization of SOC and also stabilization of carbon inputs into soil organic forms.

Figure 26 : SYMPHONY conceptual diagram with state variables (rectangles), fluxes (circles) of carbon (blue) and nitrogen (red), and incoming and outgoing fluxes (clouds). The images help to understand the state variable concerned.

In SYMPHONY pools and flows are expressed in carbon and nitrogen, and involve stoichiometric relations. Dynamics of C and N are driven by two functional groups of microorganisms: SOM

decomposers and SOM builders. SOM builders are a microbial functional group capable of mobilizing fresh organic matter compounds (FOM), forming or leaving a more stable or recalcitrant SOM. They are N limited, because fresh organic matter is rich in carbon, and are therefore in competition with plants for soil mineral N (Φ_{imf}) with an advantage for plant. SOM decomposers will attack the stable SOM (Φ_A) using the energy, in form of carbon, of FOM (Φ_d). They are C limited because SOM is rich in nitrogen and they are in competition with SOM builders for the FOM carbon with an advantage for SOM builders. They release mineral N and carry out the mineralization process (Φ_{ims}). Mineral N can be deposited (Φ_i) or leached (Φ_l). Both microbial groups have a respiration carbon flow (Φ_{rb} & Φ_{rd}). This model only simulates plants through a single compartment (Plant), which only concerns the carbon contained in the biomass. The plant grows through photosynthesis (Φ_{ph}) and nitrogen uptake (Φ_{up}). Carbon flows out of this compartment through respiration (Φ_{respi}), export or organic matter deposition on/in the soil ($mp\ C_p$).

In this model, compartments or state variables have a fixed N/C ratio and will be limited by either nitrogen or carbon. Model's application conditions are the following: (1) the N/C ratio α must always be greater than β , otherwise nitrogen and carbon limitation will be disrupted, (2) The Φ_A flux parameter A must also always be greater than the Φ_{sd} or Φ_{sb} flux parameter s, otherwise SOM_decomposers end up no longer mineralizing nitrogen.

The models used those criteria to evaluate its feasibility:

1. The coexistence of plant and decomposers.
2. Ecosystems must be able to resist to a long-term (10 years) net nutrient output.
3. The continuous accumulation of SOM in undisturbed soils when there is net nutrient input to ecosystems, so there is no theoretical limit to soil C accumulation
4. Eventual steady state for SOM pool, especially in agricultural systems where N inputs balance N outputs.

It should be noted, however, that SYMPHONY has only been validated theoretically, and has only been studied under stable conditions in order to determine the conditions under which the priming effect occurs. Parametrization has been realized from published studies and specific measurements made at a studied experimental site (Table 7). The site is a temperate permanent grassland located at 1040 m in France (Laqueuille, 45°38'N, 2°44'E).

Table 7 : 14 parameters of SYMPHONY model

abbreviation	Definition	Values
alpha	N/C ratio of SOM, SOM_builder and SOM_décomposers (s-u)	0.0909091
beta	N/C ratio of FOM et Plant (s-u)	0.0142857
rp	Coefficient of Plant's respiration (s-u)	0.00369772

ep	Export coefficient of plant materials (s-u)	0.000798799
mp	Dead plant material coefficient (s-u)	0.00505757
k	Photosynthetic coefficient (s-u)	0.0121216
Ca	Atmospheric concentration of CO2 (s-u)	400
e	Uptake's coefficient of Plant for nitrogen	0.0289652
s	Production coefficient of SOM by SOMbuilders and SOM_decomposers	0.016906
r	Respiration coefficient of the Plant	0.0368857
u	Consumption coefficient of FOM by SOMbuilders in carbon limited conditions	0.00929094
y	Consumption coefficient of FOM by SOMdecomposers in carbon limited conditions	0.00042286,
i	Immobilization/mineralization rate of nitrogen by SOMbuilder et SOMdecomposers	0.0110068
l	Leaching nitrogen rate	0.00262647
A	Consumption rate of SOM by SOMdecomposers	0.0317917
Phi_i	Nitrogen rate (daily) add in ecosystem (deposition, rain, ect...) (N g.m ⁻²)	0.0627704

3.2.4 ModVege, an above-ground plant model

ModVege is designed to simulate the growth of above-ground plant biomass, the effect of mowing, and the digestibility and quality of mowed biomass from permanent grassland with permanent plant cover. It is based on physiological processes considered most essential for plant biomass growth. It is composed of a series of differential equations described in a first publication (Jouven et al., 2006a), and validated by comparison with data in a second publication (Jouven et al., 2006b).

Figure 27 : Conceptual scheme ModVege model with state variables (rectangles), flows (circles and arrows) of biomass (solid arrows) and informative (dotted arrows), response functions (diamonds) and input data (octagons). Images help to understand the state variable concerned.

ModVege simulates 4 biomass compartments: green vegetative biomass (BGV), green reproductive biomass (BGR), dry vegetative biomass (BDV) and dry reproductive biomass (BDR). These 4 compartments have different digestibility. They will have an associated age (AgeGV, AgeGR, AgeDV, AgeDR). The growth of the vegetative compartments BGV and BGR (GRO), is a function of light (PAR) and leaf area (LAI) and will be limited by environmental factors (ENV). These environmental factors concern water ($f(W)$), light inhibition ($f(PAR)$), temperature ($f(T)$) and soil fertility (NI). Allocation (REP)

between reproductive (GROgr) and vegetative (GROgv) growth is activated when the sum of degree-days (ST) exceeds a threshold. Biomass passes from green to dry compartments (BDV, BDR) via senescence flows (SENgv, SENgr) according to their age. Finally, it exits the model through abscission flows (ABSdv, ABSdr). Parameters are functional traits of a single species or of a species community. A functional trait is a morphological (SLA, height), physiological (C or N acquisition capacity), biochemical (C or N content) or phenological (growth/reproduction period) attribute of a plant, species or community (Maire, 2009). Parametrization has been realized according to Cruz et al. (2002) classification of temperate grassland into four groups on the basis of their functional traits. We choose to keep the parametrization realized by Jouven et al. (2006) in the sensibility analysis (Table 8).

ModVege involve 5 a priori hypothesis:

1. Compartment and their digestibility are affected by their age which is calculated in function of temperature sum during a year
2. Grassland's biomass dynamic is explained by mean values traits of species composition
3. Changes in biomass digestibility are explained by different proportions of biomass compartment (BGV, BGR, BDV and BDR)
4. Soil nitrogen availability is constant and limit the growth (NI)
5. Growth flows follow an empiric seasonal scheme which is manipulate as functional trait which represents the setting aside of resources or the mobilization of these reserves for a boost at the start of the growth period.

Bittar et al. (2018) have tested ModVege on 125 grassland situation and reasonable biomass production prediction. However, the model overestimate drought effect. And this conclusion is confirm by Calanca et al. (2016) which have tested the ability of ModVege to simulate a permanent grassland production under drought condition. They try to modify the water stress equations and fit results with data. This modification does not change significantly their result and they evaluate that ModVege overestimate drought effect. However, it overestimates LAI and growth start on all cases. In general, growth and water reserve have good magnitude evaluation. They suggest to add roots and a plant parameter of stress tolerance. Finally, they both criticize the NI parameters of constant soil fertility which probably vary with water availability.

Abbreviation	Definition	Value
K_GV	Senescing rate of BGV (s-u)	0.0020
K_GR	Senescing rate of BGR (s-u)	0.0010
T0	Activation temperature threshold of biomass growth (°C)	4.0000
T1	Minimum temperature threshold of growth biomass optimum (°C)	10.0000
T2	Maximum temperature threshold of growth biomass optimum (°C)	20.0000

maxT	Maximum temperature threshold of growth biomass (°C)	40.0000
LLS	Leaf life span (°C.d ⁻¹)	790.0000
OMD_DV	Digestibility coefficient of biomass BDV (s-u)	0.4500
OMD_DR	Digestibility coefficient of biomass BDR (s-u)	0.4000
max_OMD_GV	Maximum digestibility coefficient of biomass BGV (s-u)	0.8800
min_OMD_GV	Minimum digestibility coefficient of biomass BGV (s-u)	0.6600
max_OMD_GR	Maximum digestibility coefficient of biomass BGR (s-u)	0.8800
min_OMD_GR	Minimum digestibility coefficient of biomass BGR (s-u)	0.4900
ST2	End of the reproductive period (°C.d ⁻¹)	1450.0000
ST1	Beginning of the reproductive period (°C.d ⁻¹)	775.0000
percent_LAM	Percentage of laminae (%)	0.6800
SLA	Leaf surface area (m ² .g ⁻¹)	0.0256
k	Loss coefficient of use light efficiency (s-u)	0.6
gamma_GV	Respiration rate of BGV (DM kg.ha ⁻¹)	0.4000
gamma_GR	Respiration rate of BGR (DM kg.ha ⁻¹)	0.2000
KIDV	Abscission rate of BDV (s-d)	0.0010
KIDR	Abscission rate of BDR (s-d)	0.0005
minSEA	Minimum value of fSEA, in winter (s-u)	0.6700
maxSEA	Maximum value of fSEA, in spring/summer (s-u)	1.3300
BDGV	Mowing threshold with 5 cm of remaining biomass for BGV (DM g.m ⁻³)	1025.0000
BDGR	Mowing threshold with 5 cm of remaining biomass for BGR (DM g.m ⁻³)	1150.0000
BDDV	Mowing threshold with 5 cm of remaining biomass for BDV (DM g.m ⁻³)	250.0000
BDDR	Mowing threshold with 5 cm of remaining biomass for BDR (DM g.m ⁻³)	225.0000
NI	Nutritional index (nitrogen)	0.7500
RUEmax	Maximum radiation use efficiency (g.MJ ⁻¹)	3.0000
WHC	Water holding capacity (mm)	60.0000

3.2.5 Nitrogen fixation, implementation of a new function related to diversity

As we wanted to manipulate different functional groups, we interest our self on legumes group which is usually found in temperate permanent grassland. Symbiotic fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by legumes is a function we need to add to our plant part. Nitrogen fixation is carried out by symbiotic bacteria in structures called nodules, and requires a deal of energy which is supplied by the plant in the form of carbohydrates (carbon products). Acquiring this nitrogen is therefore costlier for the plant than extracting the nitrogen available directly from the soil, but it's a good strategy in case of competition or nitrogen depletion. The number of nodules and their use is regulated by the plant via carbohydrate supply and control of di-oxygen concentration and, by feedback, plant growth will also be regulated by the number and performance of these nodules (Schwember, et al. 2019). More specifically, N₂ fixation depends on the plant's demand for nitrogen, as well as on the stoichiometry between the elements required for plant growth, such as its C/N ratio (Soussana & Tallec, 2010). This element requirement is conditioned by photosynthetic activity, phenological stage and the amount of nitrogen readily available in the soil. Moreover, nitrogen demand decreases as nitrogen is remobilized during leaf senescence. We compared 4 models of nitrogen fixation and their equations (Eq.5, 6, 7 & 8). For an easy understanding, factors with the same meaning have been renamed in the same way.

Thornley (1995)
$$N_{fix} = E_{fix} \times B_{root} \quad (5)$$

Lazzarotto 2009
$$N_{fix} = f(T_{soil}) \times E_{fix} \times B_{root} \times N_{rate\ max} \times \left(1 - f \times \frac{MineralN}{MineralN + k}\right) \quad (6)$$

JF Soussana 2009
$$N_{fix} = (1 - b) \times N_c \times \frac{dB}{dt} \times \frac{1}{1 + MineralN/k} \quad (7)$$

Schwinning 1996
$$N_{fix} = E_{fix} \times B_C \times \left(1 - f \times \frac{MineralN}{MineralN + k}\right) \quad (8)$$

In most equations, we find the parameter E, which is the rate of fixation at each time step. In these four equations, nitrogen fixation depends on the mass (Broot, BC, B) of the roots, the carbon contained in the plant or the whole plant, respectively. In the three most recent equations, there is a dependence on the mineral nitrogen contained in the soil (MineralN) in non-linear Holling II form, with a constant k corresponding to the mineral nitrogen concentration in the soil at which fixation is equal to half the maximum fixation (Michaelis-Menten). In Soussana's 2009 model, there is a dependence on the nitrogen required by the plant according to the critical concentration Nc, which is a non-linear relationship between nitrogen uptake and biomass. This critical concentration decreases as biomass increases (Ciampitti et al., 2022) and changes during plant growth with the parameter b. In Lazzarotto's (2009) model, fixation depends on soil temperature and an N rate max parameter, which is the maximum rate of N uptake from the soil by roots. In Lazzarotto's (2009) and Schwinning's (1996) models, f corresponds to the maximum fraction of soil N uptake. A review of articles (Liu et al., 2011) comparing 11 mechanistic models with N-fixation, concludes that N-fixation equations are constructed with potential N-fixation multiplied by limiting factors of temperature, water stress, the presence of mineral N in the root zone, the carbon contained in the plant available to feed nodules and the influence of plant growth stage. Potential nitrogen fixation is determined mainly by the plant's nitrogen requirement and its nitrogen-fixing efficiency, which in more detailed models is also linked to nodule development. In order to minimize the number of parameters required, and since it refers to the carbon contained in the BC biomass, we selected the equation proposed by Schwinning (Eq 8 & 9). We have, however, removed the parameter f as it relates to the soil nitrogen extraction equation and is not present in the equation we have chosen in the ModVege - SYMPHONY coupling. To enable the model to work with legumes as well as with non-nitrogen-fixing plants, we have added the LEG parameter (1 or 0), which enables symbiotic fixation to be activated or not.

$$N_{fix} = E_{fix} \times (BGV + BGR) \times \left(1 - \frac{MineralN}{MineralN + k_{fix}}\right) \times LEG \quad (9)$$

The choice of this equation underlies several points that can be discuss:

- We consider that age has no direct impact on the amount of N fixed.

- Stress factors (temperature, water) are not directly considered, but they do have an indirect effect on plant biomass dynamics, on which N_{fix} depends.
- The E_{fix} parameter, which is 0.0012 in the PROGRASS model, depends on root biomass. In Lazzarotto's model, the growth of the root compartment is determined by allocation equations between root and aerial compartments. For the sake of simplicity, we have chosen not to include a root compartment in our model. We have therefore kept this parameter unchanged, assuming a ratio between the aerial and root parts of 1.
- The PROGRASS k_{fix} parameter and the maximum value achieved for mineral nitrogen in the same publication are 0.006 kg.m⁻². Thus, $MineralN / (MineralN + k_{fix})$ does not exceed 0.5, the maximum value of $MineralN$ being 0.006 kgN.m⁻². We have added the nitrogen thus fixed to the legume growth equation, with the effect that legumes will be less limited by the availability of mineral nitrogen in the soil (Eq 10).

$$GRO = \min \left(P_{gro} \times f_{SEA} \times ENV; \left(E \times MineralN + N_{fix} + N_{rec} \right) \times \frac{1}{\beta_1 \times c_{croi}} \right) \quad (10)$$

As legumes are less competitive than grasses to access available soil nitrogen, the E parameter for legumes is therefore smaller than for grasses (Eq 10). In order to maintain the same competitive advantage between legumes and grasses as in the PROGRASS model, we took the ratio between the E coefficient of grasses and E coefficient of legumes in the PROGRASS model to find the E coefficient of legumes in our model (i.e. $E_{GrassesPROGRASS} = 0.0062$, $E_{LegumesPROGRASS} = 0.005$, $E_{GrassesSYMPHONY} = 0.0289652$ so $E_{LegumesSYMPHONY} = 0.0289652 / (0.0062/0.005) = 0.02335903$). The N/C ratio values between legumes and grasses are different, so legumes will have a much higher nitrogen demand.

Figure 28 : Advantage in terms of nitrogen nutrition Nitrogen used by legumes (red solid line) and grasses (black solid line), fixed by legumes (red dashed line) and taken up by legumes (red dotted line) as a function of mineral nitrogen present in the soil A) with 500 kg.ha⁻¹ of biomass and B) with 1500 kg.ha⁻¹ of biomass.

3.2.6 DYNAGRAM and COSMO, plant diversity interactions models

ModVege permit to manipulate functional traits but simulates a single species or a mean community with a constant pool of parameters over time. In this way, community and/or species abundance do

not vary during the simulation. It is then impossible to include important processes for SOM turnover, such as inter-species competition for nitrogen or differences in composition of organic matter returning to the soil. We have selected two models for this purpose: CoSMo and DYNAGRAM.

Figure 29 : Flowchart of the CoSMo approach for community simulation; M indicates the number of species present in the community. From (Confalonieri, 2014)

CoSMo is a generic model that can be coupled with a biomass growth model, giving it a multi-species dimension. Competition in this model is based on a calculation of relative abundance gain or loss with regard to the capacity of the species, relative to the capacity of other species, to develop under the conditions of the given time step. The determining factors for competition are: management practices, temperature and access to resources (light, water and nitrogen), in respective order of importance. An index of adaptation to current conditions is then calculated for each species, compared with the average aptitude of all species, and a gain/loss in relative abundance is calculated.

CosMo can be coupled to ModVege in two ways: i) either by simulating one instance of ModVege per species and then, at each time step, updating the relative abundance of each species as well as the environmental variables (e.g. water reserve), ii) or by calculating average community traits via a weighted average of species traits by their relative abundances and updating the relative abundance at each time step. The advantage of the latter version is that only one instance of ModVege is executed, although the fact that some traits are averaged is incorrect (e.g. phenology traits corresponding to temperature sums). As the execution time of ModVege is not a blocking point, we developed the code for the first case stated in R. However, the biggest problem with CoSMo concerns the number of new parameters it requires. Moreover, there is very little information on these parameters in the literature (e.g. number of days before the plant starts growing again following a mowing operation).

We also turned our attention to another model, DYNAGRAM (Moulin et al., 2021). This model is based on ModVege and adds competition for resources. Direct competition is based on access to light resources via the leaf area index (LAI), which is calculated as the ratio between leaf area and the area

occupied by plants on the ground. When the LAI of one species increases relative to another, the ratio of its LAI to the LAI_{tot}, which is the sum of the LAIs of all species, tends towards 1. P_{gro}, which is the maximum growth potential, will then be less limited. A second level of resource competition takes the form of response curves to resource limitations. The P_{gro} will be multiplied by a value between 0 and 1, 0 meaning that the resource quantity is so low that no growth is possible, while 1 implies a non-limiting resource quantity, in a similar way to the ENV calculation for ModVege. The DYNAGRAM model code and data are provided on a github platform in R language (<https://github.com/510fgillet3/DynaGraM>) and is consequently very easy to access.

Figure 30: Structure of the DynaGraM model. Rectangular plain boxes denote state variables (plant biomass, nitrogen and water reserve); rounded rectangles account for forcing variables (climate and management), intermediate variables (LAI, growth rates) or synthetic index of diversity (Simpson evenness EB); blue plain lines denote primary relations or effects and red dashed lines denote reducer effects limiting the plant growth. From (Moulin et al., 2021)

3.2.7 The Belowground biomass

The coupling of the SYMPHONY and ModVege models lacked a large unrepresented component, namely the root system. Indeed, while the ModVege model provided SYMPHONY with annual and daily dynamics, and allowed for variations in soil organic matter input and mineral nitrogen uptake, these fluxes could not be well represented without the influence of the root zone. But this work is still in progress, so we won't be presenting the results in this deliverable.

3.2.8 Coupling process

Figure 31 : Conceptual diagram of the ModVege - SYMPHONY model [final coupling] with state variables (rectangles), biomass (whole arrows) and information (dotted arrows) flows (circles and arrows), response functions (diamonds), input data (octagons). Images help to understand the state variable concerned.

We have connected ModVege and SYMPHONY. Overall, coupling means replacing SYMPHONY's simple "Plant" compartment with the ModVege model (Figure 7). Thus, the two models will mainly "communicate" via:

- the ModVege abscission biomass ($ABS_{DV} + ABS_{DR}$) expressed in $DM\ kg\ ha^{-1}$, which will be injected into SYMPHONY in the form of FOM, expressed in $g\ m^{-2}$ of C and N. This will enable us to better model biomass flows entering in the form of FOM, since these will depend on climatic conditions and plant phenology. As the quantity of carbon reaching the FOM is already in $kg\ ha^{-1}$.
- Mineral N demand. In ModVege, this was modelled by a constant NI parameter, the nitrogen nutrition index, which is a factor between 0 and 1 limiting plant growth. I have therefore replaced this constant parameter with an explicit withdrawal from SYMPHONY's "mineralN" compartment, which does not allow us to model nitrogen dynamics.

Our coupling model must meet the following criteria:

- Compliance with the criteria imposed by SYMPHONY
- Observation of seasonal dynamics in all compartments.

- Having the same order of magnitude of ModVege biomass under the same conditions.

In SYMPHONY, the nitrogen uptake equation is based on a linear relationship between mineral nitrogen and a coefficient of nitrogen extraction efficiency E by the plant, under nitrogen-limiting conditions. The photosynthetic flux Phi_{ph} is then equal to:

$$Phi_{ph} = \min \left(k \times Ca ; \frac{E \times MineralN}{\beta} + r_p \times C_p \right)$$

With k the photosynthesis rate, Ca the air CO₂ concentration, β the N/C ratio, C_p the carbon contained in the plant and r_p the respiration coefficient. The NI index is therefore suppressed and GRO growth is limited by soil nitrogen uptake (Eq 1, Eq2) via the same equation as for SYMPHONY. Biomass dependency is implicitly present, as potential GRO growth, before environmental limitation, depends on biomass (Eq ...). ModVege simulates biomass, while SYMPHONY simulates carbon and nitrogen. Biomass is converted into carbon using a ratio of carbon contained in biomass c_{croi} with a value of 0.5. (Oberberger et al., 2006). This value was found in an article on biofuel and is a commonly accepted value for grasses.

$$\text{ModVege} \quad GRO = Pgro \times fSEA \times ENV \times NI \quad (11)$$

$$\text{ModVege - SYMPHONY} \quad GRO = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} Pgro \times fSEA \times ENV \\ \frac{E \times MineralN}{\beta \times c_{croi}} \end{array} \right. \quad (12)$$

$$\text{ModVege} \quad Pgro = PARI_t \times RUEmax \times (1 - e^{-k \times LAI}) \times 10 \quad (13)$$

With β , the plant's N/C coefficient; E , the plant's nitrogen uptake efficiency; $MineralN$, the stock of mineral nitrogen available to the plant and microorganisms. As explained above, the biomass resulting from the abscission of ModVege is injected into SYMPHONY's FOM compartment and converted into carbon. Thus, with Phi_f and Phi_d , we have the FOM consumption fluxes of the two groups of microorganisms:

$$\text{SYMPHONY} \quad \frac{d FOM_C}{dt} = mp \times Cp - Phi_f - Phi_d \quad (14)$$

$$\text{ModVege - SYMPHONY} \quad \frac{d FOM_C}{dt} = C_{ABStot} - Phi_f - Phi_d \quad (15)$$

$$\text{ModVege - SYMPHONY} \quad C_{ABStot} = (ABSdr + ABSdv) \times c_{croi} \quad (16)$$

This first association model between SYMPHONY and ModVege provided consistent dynamics compared to both models, but induced a sharp decrease in above-ground plant biomass production compared to ModVege, as biomass production was found to be strongly limited by nitrogen. One of our criteria was therefore not met.

In SYMPHONY, the ratio between carbon and nitrogen is a central element. There are two N/C ratios, one for the plant (β) and one for the soil compartments (α) (Table 7). In the first coupling attempt, we

assumed a constant plant N/C between green and dry ModVege states (B_{GV} & B_{DR}). However, we know that N/C changes between senescent and green biomass. Similarly, during senescence, part of the nitrogen is recycled by the plant to the young parts. (Havé et al., 2017; Hörtensteiner & Feller, 2002). In our final coupling model, we therefore chose two different N/Cs for the green (β_{Green}) and dry parts (β_{Dry}) (Eq 7).

$$N_{rec} = c_{croi} \times (SEN_{GV} + SEN_{GR}) \times (\beta_{Green} - \beta_{Dry}) \quad (17)$$

With N_{rec} the nitrogen recycled from dry to green biomasses. To do this, simply add up the fluxes of senescent biomass (SEN_{gv} et SEN_{gr}), convert them to carbon using the c_{croi} coefficient and then calculate the excess nitrogen by multiplying by the difference between the N/C of the green compartment β_{Green} and the dry compartment β_{Dry} . Therefore, the inequality of $\beta_{Dry} < \beta_{Green}$ need to be always respected.

However, this remobilization of nitrogen has raised new questions. At the start of winter, the plant stops growing and simply ages and dies. The recycled nitrogen is therefore not useful for photosynthesis and ends up in excess. To overcome this problem, we turned to exudates. To stimulate micro-organisms, the plant exudes carbon and nitrogen in the form of low-weight compounds that are easily assimilated by micro-organisms. (Jones et al., 2004). We have therefore added an exudation of nitrogen present in excess in the plant.

$$N_{ex} = Phi_{up} + N_{rec} - GRO \times \beta_{Green} \times c_{croi} \quad (18)$$

With N_{ex} the nitrogen exuded, β_{Green} the plant's N/C; Phi_{up} the nitrogen uptake flux; GRO the biomass growth flux and c_{croi} the coefficient of conversion of plant biomass to C. However, exudation mainly concerns carbon and plays an important role for micro-organisms (Nguyen, 2003). On the same principle, the carbon exuded will be the carbon photosynthesized in excess by the plant following nitrogen limitation (Eq 9):

$$C_{ex} = \max((P_{gro} \times f_{SEA} \times ENV - GRO) \times c_{croi}; 0) \quad (19)$$

As a result, in addition to the 3 fixed N/C ratios, the FOM N/C ratio will be dynamic, as exuded N and C will cause it to vary over the course of the simulation. At each time step, this ratio will be calculated as follows:

$$\beta_{FOM} = \frac{FOM_N}{FOM_C} \quad (20)$$

Finally, we take a step-by-step approach, adapting the complexity of the model as our results come in. Our approach is summarized in Table 9.

Table 9 : Tested and done coupling work with toys models to integrate (1) SOM and SOC turnover (2) Microbial diversity (3) Plant biomass production and (4) Plant diversity

Plants Soil	An abstract single plant biomass	Explicit Aboveground-biomass with a single species or a mean community	Explicit above-ground ant belowground biomass simulation with a single species	Diversity of plants with interactions	
				Explicit Aboveground-biomass	Explicit Above-ground and below-ground biomass
No SOM and SOC turnover and a constant soil fertility	X	ModVege	ModVege – LINGRA In progress	DYNAGRAModVege	DYNAGRAModVege – LINGRA In progress
				ModVege – CoSMo	ModVege – LINGRA – CoSMo In progress
SOM and SOC turnover with microbial diversity	SYMPHONY	SYMPHONY - ModVege	SYMPHONY – ModVege – LINGRA In progress	SYMPHONY – DYNAGRAModVege	SYMPHONY – DYNAGRAModVege – LINGRA In progress
				SYMPHONY – ModVege – CoSMo	SYMPHONY – ModVege – LINGRA – CoSMo In progress

3.3 Results

Results we are presenting in this part only concern the SYMPHONY – ModVege coupling work because the addition of roots and plant diversity is still a work in progress. The aim is not to be close to observed data, but to check that the trend of the coupled model remains similar to the source models (ModVege, SYMPHONY). Our model needs to be tested under mowing and fertilization management. The case of no management is not realistic but we used it in order to have a simple comparison without involving any management.

3.3.1 Biomass simulation

ModVege and the coupling model ModVege – SYMPHONY present the same aerial compartment trends with a growth peak in the green vegetative compartment at the beginning of the season (spring, when climatic conditions are favourable), followed by an increase in the biomass of the green reproductive compartment corresponding to the breeding season (Figure 32, A, B, C, F, G).

However, there are differences in the orders of magnitude, since the value of peak biomass (BGV + BGR + BDV + BDR) per year is between 5465 kgDM.ha⁻¹ and 7432 kgDM.ha⁻¹ for ModVege (Figure 32, A), whereas for ModVege - SYMPHONY it is between 3312 kgDM.ha⁻¹ and 4362 kgDM.ha⁻¹ (Figure 32, B). With mowing, the average yield over 8 years for ModVege is 2232 kgDM.ha⁻¹ for the first mowing

(day 181), 2347 kgDM.ha⁻¹ for the second mowing (day 237) and 1352 kgDM.ha⁻¹ for the third mowing (day 303) (Figure 32, F) whereas for the ModVege - SYMPHONY coupling, it is 1118 kgDM.ha⁻¹, 1144 kgDM.ha⁻¹ and 922 kgDM.ha⁻¹ respectively (Figure 32, G). The ModVege-SYMPHONY coupling is therefore less productive than ModVege. The only different parameter affecting biomass growth between ModVege and ModVege-SYMPHONY is the NI parameter.

If we add fertilization in ModVege-SYMPHONY model at a rate of 100 kg.ha⁻¹ per day, not realistic but in order to avoid the growth limitation by nitrogen, we observe that biomass production is now higher than ModVege (Figure 32, E).

E
ModVege – SYMPHONY,
without mowing,
with fertilization

F
ModVege, with
mowing

G
ModVege-
SYMPHONY, with
mowing, without
fertilization

Figure 32 : Biomass of the 4 compartments (BGV, BGR, BDV et BDR) on 8 climatic year using data from the Marcenat station from 1993 to 2000, without mowing by A) ModVege B) ModVege – SYMPHONY and by adding a fertilisation of 100 kg.ha⁻¹ by day to remove nitrogen limitation present in C) ModVege – SYMPHONY. And with mowing on days 181, 237 and 303, without fertilization by F) ModVege G) ModVege – SYMPHONY. Parameters used and initial values are those from sensibility analysis of Jouven et al. (2006a). NB: fertilization apply rate in this case is just to make appear the strong limitation of nitrogen in our model, it is not realistic.

Indeed, replacing the NI parameter with a stoichiometric growth equation depending on nitrogen uptake leads to a nitrogen limitation, resulting in a decrease of production. This replacement simulates a variable NI across time (Figure 34). This NI of ModVege-SYMPHONY is higher than the NI of ModVege at the beginning growth period but is lower when the plant demands become stronger. The growth dynamic of ModVege-SYMPHONY in then change (Figure 33). The variable NI was calculated as the

ratio of available nitrogen (uptake + recycle nitrogen) and nitrogen needed to fulfilled photosynthetic demands of the C/N ratio.

Figure 33 : Growth difference between ModVege and ModVege-SYMPHONY. If the curve is < 0 , it means growth is higher in ModVege-SYMPHONY, if it is > 0 it means growth is higher in ModVege and if curve = 0, ModVege and ModVege-SYMPHONY growth are equal. Without mowing and without fertilization

Figure 34 : NI of ModVege (dotted black line) and variable NI of ModVege- SYMPHONY mean (dark green), median (clear green), quantile 25% and quantile 75% (dotted red line inferior and superior respectively) during a mean climatic year (mean of 8 climatic years). Without mowing and without fertilization.

However, the case of Figure 32, G of ModVege-SYMPHONY challenge us because in this system, there is no entry of nitrogen because there is no fertilization but there is an output of nitrogen through mowing with plant biomass export. Then, the system should be impoverished with time and biomass production should progressively decrease.

3.3.2 SOM and SOC annual dynamics

The SYMPHONY model had no prior annual dynamics. In the case of no mowing and no fertilization, the dynamics of organic matter stored in the soil (SOM) will stabilize after a certain time and reach a pseudo-equilibrium (Figure 35, A). The oscillation between SOMbuilders and SOMdecomposers corresponds to the plant's annual cycle (Figure 35, B). In the first phase, SOM builders increase as FOM is abundant and there is no competition for mineral nitrogen with the plant. In the second phase of the plant's growth, SOM builders decrease because of the lack of nitrogen due to competition with the plant. SOM decomposers then increase, as they have less competition for FOM carbon and will mineralize nitrogen. When the plant's growth phase is over, it will need less nitrogen, so SOM builders will increase again.

Figure 35 : evolution of SOM (kg/ha) (A&C), SOM builders, SOM decomposer and mineral N (B&C) on 3*8 climatic year in two management situation (explained in subtitles).

Now, in the case of mowing without fertilisation (Figure 32, G) of ModVege-SYMPHONY where there is no entry of nitrogen because there is no fertilization but there is an output of nitrogen through plant biomass export. The system maintains the biomass production because of a consumption of SOM by SOM decomposers which are constantly outnumber SOM builders (Figure 35, C & D). Mineralization is then maintained to a reasonable rate. SOM builders are going to be limited by the quantity of FOM but most of all they are now over limited by the nitrogen because FOM carbon the C/N ratio mean of the FOM is about 249 with mowing while it is about 113 without mowing (Figure 36).

Figure 36 : evolution of FOM in two management case (A&B) on 3*8 climatic years

Indeed, plants have less recycled nitrogen and so less exuded nitrogen. But the exportation of carbon through mowing is maintain by carbon exudation. So, after 112 years, our system completely exhausts the SOM's nitrogen resources that were fixed at 70 tC.ha⁻¹ according to the French national map of soil carbon stocks integrated into the FAO world map (<https://www.gissol.fr/donnees/cartes/la-carte-nationale-des-stocks-de-carbone-des-sols-integree-dans-la-carte-mondiale-de-la-fao-4335>).

With our model, we have studied the storage/unstorage of carbon in the model according to several scenarios. This storage/unstorage is due to the activity of SOMdecomposers (SOM destorage to mineralize nitrogen) and SOMbuilders (SOM storage following mineral N consumption). In the initial version of SYMPHONY, the relationship between SOM consumption by SOMdecomposers is established by multiplying a constant parameter A with the quantity of SOMdecomposers. SYMPHONY assumes that the SOM stock is very large. We therefore tested several values of parameter A but we needed to respect the SYMPHONY condition of parameter $A > \text{parameter } s$ (see Table 7). The results in Table 11 are consistent with the orders of magnitude reported in the literature (Pellerin et al., 2020). With mowing and without fertilization, dynamics are slowed as parameter A decreases. Without mowing and fertilization, the model reaches equilibrium. On the other hand, following the addition of fertilization, organic carbon is then stored in the SOM, ranging from 0.2 to 0.8 t C.ha⁻¹.yr⁻¹ in the case of mowed grassland to 1.3 to 1.6 tC.ha⁻¹.yr⁻¹ for grassland without mowing.

Table 10 : Carbon storage/destorage on 8*3 years on different management, with different values of parameters A. Mowing are realized on day 181, 237 and 303. Fertilization were realized on day 100, 200 and 250 with 50 N kg.ha⁻¹ in order to compensate mowing effect

A	Without mowing		Mowing	
	Without fertilization	fertilization	Without fertilization	fertilization
+ 10%	- 2.4t/24y	38.35 t/24y	-25 t/24y	5.4 t/24y
0.03497	-0.10 t/y	1.61 t/y	-1.06 t/y	0.22 t/y
SYMPHONY	- 3.09 t/24y	38.51 t/24y	-22 t/24y	6.22 t/24y
0.03179	- 0.12 t/y	1.60 t/y	-0.93 t/y	0.25 t/y
- 10%	- 3.85 t/24y	38.04 t/24y	-18.2 t/24y	7.2 t/24y
0.02861	- 0.16 t/y	1.58 t/y	-0.76 t/y	0.30 t/y
- 45%	t/24y	37.01 t/24y	1.33 t/24y	21.36 t/24y
0.0174845	1.40 t/y	t/y	t/y	t/y

In dark grey: SOM reach an equilibrium point depending on initial values of state variable (see Figure 35, A). In middle grey: values are not reliable because the model crash. In clear grey: there is a constant storage of SOM. In white: There is a constant destorage.

3.3.3 Nitrogen fixation effect

We will now compare results when we add a nitrogen fixation function to the plants. The model is still the ModVege-SYMPHONY but with a fixation function in addition. We tested it with a 100% legumes presence and we use a reduce factor of 0.5 to simulate a grassland with 50% legumes in the ModVege plant community. The main difference between those two community is the nitrogen fixation. We did not adapt the C/N ratio or the phenology in a first place. ModVege's grass community is limited by nitrogen, when we add this nitrogen fixation function, we observe a clear increase of total biomass (Figure 37). Increase in parameters e_{fix} (parameter related to the root) increase a little bit biomass and reducing parameter k_{fix} (capacity of fixing nitrogen) reduce biomass but those variation are not huge, maybe because of the intrinsic growth plant in ModVege with carbon and nitrogen uptake. In PROGRASS, mineral nitrogen reaches values of $60 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$, while our mineral nitrogen without fertilization remains around $20 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$.

A 100% legumes, without mowing, without fertilization,

B 50% legumes, without mowing, without fertilization

C 100% legumes with mowing, without fertilization

D 50% legumes, with mowing, without fertilization, 50% legumes

Figure 37 : Evolution of biomass ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$) on 8 years climatic data with mowing on day 181, 237 and 303 (C&D) , different set of parameters for N fixation (k_{fix} and e_{fix} , see Eq. 7) and percentages of legumes.

We have studied the storage/unstorage of carbon with the nitrogen function addition according to several scenarios and several values of parameter A (see Table 7). The results in Table 11 show that in all situations, except mowing without fertilization with 50% legumes, the carbon is store into the soil. Those results need to be taken carefully, for now, we did not saw such result in literature.

Table 11 : Carbon storage/destorage on 8*3 years on different management, with different values of parameters A. Mowing are realized on day 181, 237 and 303. Fertilization were realized on day 100, 200 and 250 with 50 N kg.ha-1 in order to compensate mowing effect

A	Without mowing				Mowing			
	Without fertilization		fertilization		Without fertilization		fertilization	
	100% Legumes	50% Legumes	100% Legumes	50% Legumes	100% Legumes	50% Legumes	100% Legumes	50% Legumes
+ 10% 0.03497	38.64 t/24y t/y	19.78 t/24y t/y	51.21t/24y t/y	51.30 t/24y t/y	5.21 t/24y t/y	-6.29 t/24y t/y	15.42 t/24y t/y	22.47 t/24y t/y
SYMPHONY 0.03179	39.10 t/24y t/y	19.59 t/24y t/y	54.10 t/24y t/y	53.70 t/24y t/y	5.49 t/24y t/y	-5.43 t/24y t/y	16.77 t/24y t/y	24.52 t/24y t/y
- 10% 0.02861	40.52 t/24y t/y	19.48 t/24y t/y	56.32 t/24y t/y	55.41 t/24y t/y	5.86 t/24y t/y	-4.16 t/24y t/y	17.86 t/24y t/y	25.91 t/24y t/y
- 45% 0.0174845	40.21 t/24y t/y	19.02 t/24y t/y	61.51 t/24y t/y	58.31 t/24y t/y	8.21 t/24y t/y	2.87 t/24y t/y	20.72 t/24y t/y	28.07 t/24y t/y

In dark grey: In middle grey: values are not reliable because the model crash. In clear grey: there is a constant storage of SOM. In white: There is a constant destorage.

Indeed, in this model, SOM builders outnumbered SOM decomposers leading to constant SOM construction. Without mowing SOM builders have plenty of FOM available, super rich in nitrogen with a mean C/N ratio of 53 and competition with plant is relaxed because the parameter e is lower than for ModVege’s grass community. SOM decomposers are then low but it does not affect plant growth because the plant compensate the mineral nitrogen depletion with fixation. With mowing, there is less FOM available for SOM builders but plant growth does not suffer that much of it (Figure 37).

C ModVege-SYMPHONY with mowing, without fertilization

D ModVege-SYMPHONY with mowing, without fertilization

Figure 38 : evolution of SOM (kg/ha) (A&C), SOM builders, SOM decomposer and mineral N (B&C) on 3*8 climatic year in two management situations (explained in subtitles).

But as we did not adapt the entire model to integrate a real legumes groups (phenological parameters or C/N ratio), so the biomass dynamics is still similar to ModVege community group tested and the benefit effect of nitrogen fixation function is surely overestimating.

3.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Our aim was to design a prototype mechanistic model to simulate the dynamics of carbon sequestration and biomass production in relation to plant functional diversity, and to evaluate mowing and fertilization management in this system. Our approach was to couple two pre-existing models, ModVege and SYMPHONY, with a multi-species dynamics model incorporating the hypothesis of competition for resources. Our objective is only half fulfilled for now because we could not introduce plant diversity in our model.

3.4.1 Encouraging results and critical point of progress

With our work, we permit to create a new model with the coupling of two already existing model ModVege and SYMPHONY, an aerial biomass model with plant traits and a SOM and SOC model with two functional microbial groups affecting mineralization and immobilization of both C and N. Our final coupling between ModVege and SYMPHONY enabled us to simulate reasonable values of carbon storage and removal, with values of $\pm 2 \text{ tC} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{year}^{-1}$ (Pellerin et al., 2020). We have also produced correct biomass orders of magnitude compared with the biomass simulated with ModVege without coupling. The annual balance of biomass in simulations with mowing and without fertilization corroborates with an experiment conducted on permanent grassland in Rothamsted, Germany, which

shows that despite two mowing per year and no fertilization, there is no significant decline in yield from year to year over a period from 1891 to 1992. This equilibrium is consistent with one of the conditions of the SYMPHONY model, which was that the nitrogen-free dynamic should last at least 10 years without being affected, and with the construction of the model which studies the priming effect. In fact, the maintenance of yield is due to the contribution of carbon exuded into the FOM, which provides the energy (carbon) to enable the SOM to be consumed by the micro-organisms. The average amount of carbon exuded per year by grasses simulated by our model is $4142 \text{ kgC}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{an}^{-1}$, which represents 42% of gross assimilated carbon (without plant respiration) and 53% of net assimilated carbon (with plant respiration). The model appears to overestimate this flux, since the orders of magnitude for exuded carbon in the literature are around $1500 \text{ kgC}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ (Kuzyakov and Domanski, 2000). Despite this, our hypothesis (photosynthesized carbon that cannot be mobilized as biomass is rhizodeposited) allows us to simulate rhizodeposition during plant growth, which is realistic. However, the amount of rhizodeposited carbon surely depends on other factors. Moreover, the transfer of photosynthesis assimilate into the soil is not instantaneous (Kuzyakov and Gavrichkova, 2010), which we have not considered in our model. Finally, according to studies, around 11% of net assimilated carbon is allocated to roots (Jones, Nguyen and Finlay, 2009), with rhizodeposition accounting for 3 to 5% of gross assimilated carbon (without respiration) and 5 to 10% of net assimilated carbon (with respiration) (Jones, Hodge and Kuzyakov, 2004). Another paper indicates that 17% of net assimilated carbon is lost by roots (12% via respiration and 5% via rhizodeposition) (Baptist et al., 2015). This suggests that a large proportion of carbon is breathed in by the roots, and that respiration in the ModVege model may therefore be underestimated. Despite these points, the behaviour of carbon storage in the presence of legumes or grasses with or without mowing is consistent. Indeed, the presence of legumes promotes carbon storage (Rodríguez et al., 2022). But several processes lack precision and important factors for SOM and SOC dynamics are missing. Indeed, aerial biomass is not enough to study the effect of plant diversity on organic carbon and nitrogen cycle in soil.

3.4.2 Working in progress with root addition

In our model, we didn't physically represent roots, as this meant rethinking the allocation of carbon from photosynthesis in ModVege, which only simulates above-ground biomass. We considered incorporating a leaf/root ratio, but the fate of these roots during mowing, as well as the numerous studies explaining that the allocation of growth between roots and leaves is driven by many other factors such as competition between plants, resource availability, age and phenological stage of the plant, discouraged us from doing so. With a simple coefficient, the roots would have died at the same time as the leaves, which doesn't seem right. In fact, there is no consensus on this, and only one study

reported a higher root death rate during mowing (Xiaozhong Liu, 2002). However, the contribution of biomass within the FOM is significantly via the roots. During this year, an internship student from Avril 2024 to September 2024 began this work to add the root part in our model. He selected two mechanistic model's equation, the Yin's model (Yin & Schapendonk, 2004) and LINGRA (Schapendonk et al., 1998) and (see Table 9).

3.4.3 For the future, legumes and plant trait distribution

In our integration of legumes, we did not consider several factors identified as important in the literature (see chapter before). Despite, in our equation, the benefit of the nitrogen fixation function is not limited, while Rodríguez et al. (2022) study the fact that legumes effect is limited on biomass productivity. It is because when did not calibrate a real legumes group by adjusting the phenology or the C/N ratio. To continue this work, an internship is scheduled with the MODIMIV program.

In our two selected multi-species models, CosMo and DYNAGRAM, competition is modelled differently. In the DYNAGRAM model, competition is for resources. The ratio of the species' LAI to the total LAI is used to calculate photosynthesis, and will limit the growth of a species that is more efficient or more abundant than the others (Moulin et al., 2021). In the CosMo model, the calculation of a plant adaptation coefficient makes it possible to gain or lose in relative abundance (Confalonieri, 2014). But there are other competition models. In our prototype, there is competition for nitrogen, with a competitive advantage for grasses thanks to their greater nitrogen extraction efficiency coefficient than that of legumes, and for light because the species with the most biomass will be able to capture more light in the DYNAGRAM equation. Organic inputs to the FOM will induce indirect facilitation. We could also put forward the hypothesis of competition through growth (GRO) or look into a competition hypothesis to be explored for light, which is that of asymmetrical competition. That is, when the plant is taller, it will have a disproportionately greater advantage over smaller plants (May, Grimm and Jeltsch, 2009). Also, our prototype allows us to manipulate certain traits of the species or groups of species under consideration. However, we have not analysed which plant traits most influence SOM and SOC dynamics. This work will be continued in a thesis funded by the Biosefair program and by VetAgroSup University at UREP.

3.4.4 Acknowledgment

We need to thanks the DIMIVEA and MODIMIV projects on the initiative of Gianni BELLOCCHI to co-finance two internships to achieve this work.

4 Adapting the classical model RothC

4.1 Introduction

The RothC model recognises 5 SOC pools of which the BIO pool represents carbon stored in the living microbial biomass. As the model itself was developed c. half a century ago, one could argue that the RothC concept falls short in taking the latest scientific knowledge on SOC-dynamics into account, e.g., soil biodiversity, roots, dead microbial biomass, and quality of the carbon input.

In the model, soil organic carbon is split into four active compartments and a small amount of inert organic matter (IOM). The four active compartments are Decomposable Plant Material (DPM), Resistant Plant Material (RPM), Microbial Biomass (BIO) and Humified Organic Matter (HUM). Each compartment decomposes by a first-order process with its own characteristic rate. The IOM compartment is resistant to decomposition. The structure of the decomposition process as included in the model is shown in Figure 1 (Coleman & Jenkinson, 2014).

Figure 39 : Schematic representation of the decomposition process in the Roth-C model (Coleman & Jenkinson, 2014).

To run the model, first an initialization step is required. With this step the model is parameterized to local conditions by running it with local data until equilibrium in SOC- contents is reached. This may involve a period of 10.000 – 50.000 years. Alternatively, pedo-transfer functions on the base of SOC- and clay-content may be used (Weihermüller et al., 2013).

Subsequently, scenario analyses may be performed, using monthly and/or yearly input data of organic matter from crop and manure. We used the model script version in R (Sierra et al., 2012; R Core team, 2020), to which adaptations were made for diversified C-input from crop residues, and for the inclusion of the microbiome. The plant residue input is the amount of C that is put into the soil per month (10^3 C ha⁻¹). The amount of farmyard manure (10^3 C ha⁻¹) is treated differently from inputs of fresh plant

residues. The decomposability of crop residues and input from farmyard manure is characterized by the DPM/RPM ratio of the materials. For agricultural purposes, a value of 1.44 to the DPM/RPM ratio of crop residues may be used (Coleman & Jenkinson, 2014).

4.2 Materials & Methods

4.2.1 Modelling Strategy

This research focusses on inclusion, in whatever form, of the soil microbiome data in the model. The working hypothesis is that the soil microbiome has an impact on carbon sequestration. This stimulation could take effect in multiple ways, e.g., diversity, C biomass, activity, etc. It is therefore important to explore and test a variety of soil microbiome indicators. From a theoretical point of view, there are several options for the inclusion of the soil microbiome: the BIO pool size, add another pool, change the partitioning over BIO and HUM, etc. Preliminary calculations showed that these factors probably do not have a distinct impact on the outcome of the modelling. These options were therefore not further investigated. Instead, explorations were made regarding the inclusion of a rate modifying factor (RMF) called 'BIO'. This RMF is to be allocated next to the other RMFs in the model. In the exponential equation in ROTHC, RMFs are treated multiplicatively and so would an RMF_{BIO} be. By definition, an RMF of 1 corresponds to the model 'Business As Usual' (BAU).

To explore the possible use and impact of a modifying factor for the soil microbiome (RMF_{BIO}) on the results of SOC-modelling comparison was made of modelling results using data from LTEs. The modelling results are compared to measured SOC-values during the experimental period by computing root mean squared errors (RMSE) between modelled and measured values. A rate modifying factor (RMF) was used as a correction factor to improve the fit. A RMF of 1 corresponds to no correction, i.e. BAU (i.e. original model). The optimal RMF per treatment was then defined as the RMF with minimal RMSE for that treatment. Subsequently, correlations analysis was performed between the optimal RMF and microbiome indicators. If substantial and significant correlations are found, than the RMF may considered to be, at least partially, related to the soil microbiome and the subscript 'BIO' is added to the RMF. The threshold for a substantial correlation was set at 0.4 (abs). When testing a high number of variables as in this case for the microbiome, with every single test the chance of incorrectly 'proving' significance increases. Therefore, a correction is required that takes the number of tests into account. In this research, a p-value of 0.001 would be a good threshold. The model is set up with a monthly time-step. Initial SOC pool sizes were determined at treatment level using the PTFs by Weihermüller et al. (2013). Data for mean monthly potential evapotranspiration were taken from Müller (1982).

Finally, the impact of the soil microbiome on SOC-dynamics was assessed as the difference between the models BAU and with RMF_{BIO}. This was done by modelling over the a period with known weather data , i.e., 2000 – 2020, to avoid the effect of uncertainties in future climate data on the outcomes.

4.2.2 Soil sampling along a European gradient

AgroEcoSeqC includes 9 LTE’s on an agroecological gradient are sampled for soil and crop analysis. (Figure 2). Several criteria were considered for selection: i) availability of historical datasets on C-inputs and C-sequestration (LTEs); ii) introduction of crop diversity (cover crops, intercropping, agroforestry); iii) reduction of soil disturbance (reduced tillage, no tillage) iv) organic inputs (plant residues, animal manure, composts, bioinoculants). Each AGROECOseqC site includes a “control” site, where agroecological intensification was not applied (tillage, monocropping, no service crop introduction, no organic inputs), and several field replicates (see table below) allowing to test the effect of site-scale ecological intensification on ecosystem variables. Of these LTE’s, four had (most of) the required input data available and consequently were used for the modelling exercise. This includes the LTE Tillage and Cover Crop management (Lithouania), LTE Clever Cover Cropping (Netherlands), LTE MO (Belgium), and New Experimental Field Fungi and Cover Cropping System (Turkey).

Figure 40 : Selection of field experiments in AgroEcoSeqC.

Soil samples were taken at the time of maximum plant growth in the layer 0-20 cm, and analysed for a wide range of indicators by various laboratories of partners within AgroEcoSeqC. For The Netherlands, the period of maximum plant growth for the cover crops sown in September is in December. In this month, activity of the soil microbiome is expected to be low, due to low temperatures. This implies that measured values of microbiome and other soil indicators may be

considered as minimum reference values. This could be useful to determine a standardised sampling period if indicator-specific RMF can be established. Most of the indicators are directly related to the soil microbiome while others relate to qualities of organic matter. No discrimination is made beforehand. All data are available at the AgroEcoSeqC repository.

4.2.3 Description of LTE for modelling

4.2.3.1 LTE Tillage and Cover Crops (Lithuania)

The experiment of tillage – cover crop management has been established in 2013 in Central part of Lithuania, in Akademija (55°23'50"N, 23°51'40"E). The field experiment was situated in the warm agroclimatic zone, which has less precipitation compared to the average. Mean annual air temperature ranged from 7.4 to 9.3 °C and annual precipitation was between 503 and 749 mm. According to the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (<https://www.isric.org/explore/wrb>), the soil is classified as an *Endocalcari – Epihypogleyic Cambisol*. The soil has a loam texture (47% sand, 35% silt, 18% clay), pH 6.7, 1.61 g kg⁻¹ N, 237 mg kg⁻¹ P₂O₅, and 314 mg.kg⁻¹ K₂O. The experiment includes 5 different tillage treatments (conventional tillage (ploughing at 22–24 cm), shallow ploughing (16–18 cm), harrowing at 8–10 cm, harrowing at 14–16 cm and no tillage) and 2 sub-treatments – without and with cover coping (CC) (Slepetiene et al., 2024). Two factorial field experiment is arranged as a split plot design in four replications (blocks). The gross area of each tillage plot was 10 × 21 m and 10 × 10.5 m of tillage–cover crop subplots. Assessments and analyses were proceeded from the samples collected in the sub-plots of 5 × 9 m (45 m²). Cereal cropping sequences consisting of five-member crop rotations (winter wheat – winter oil seed rape (± cover crop) - spring wheat (± cover crop) - spring barley (± cover crop) - field pea).

A timeline of the whole period of tillage – cover cropping field experiment is presented in Figure 3.

Crop maintenance, including the application of herbicides, fungicides, insecticides, and growth regulators, was conducted according to the needs. For the whole 5 years crop cycle (each crop rotation) total amount of applied fertilizers was approximately: N - 676, P - 261 and K - 547 kg a.i. ha⁻¹. All crop residues and straw after the harvest remained in the same areas where they have grown.

Figure 41: Timeline of LTE Tillage and Cover Crop Management (Lithuania). Dark green: cover crop growing period (for cover crop sub-plots); Black striped: main crop growing period; Light green: intermediate period; Tillage: tillage operations, except no-till treatment.

Soil and plant analysis included many soil biological parameters, among which Cmic, bacterial and fungal biomass. Bulk density was measured at treatment level. Weather data were taken from the Dotnuva Meteorological station, which is located in a distance of 0.5 km from the field experiment. In AgroEcoSeqC, the following treatments were selected for soil and plant sampling:

T1: no tillage without cover crops

T2: no tillage + cover crops

T3: conventional tillage without cover crops (Control).

4.2.3.2 LTE Clever Cover Cropping (The Netherlands)

The experiment Clever Cover Cropping focuses on the use of cover crops during the winter period in arable cropping systems. The field experiment is conducted on a sandy soil (Haplic podzol, 83% sand, 12% silt, 2% clay, pH 5.3, 1.09 g kg⁻¹ N, 58 mg.kg⁻¹ P of which 2.2 mg.kg⁻¹ plant-available P, and 91 mg.kg⁻¹ K) at the Nergena Farm, Wageningen, The Netherlands, 51°59'42.7"N, 5°39'35.7"E (Elhakeem et al., 2023). The long term annual average temperature is 9.4°C and annual average rainfall is 780 mm. Drainage pipes are installed 100 cm deep. The field has a history of conventional arable farming, winterwheat being the last commercially crop grown before the start of the experiment in 2016. The experiment consists of eight cover crop treatments (Porre, 2020) : 3 monoculture species, Radish (*Raphanus sativus*, (R)), Vetch (*Vicia sativa*, (V)), and Oats (*Avena strigoza*, (O)) 3 mixtures of 2 species (VR, RO, VO) and 1 mixture of the 3 species (VOR), and a fallow control (F) (Figure 4). The treatments are replicated five times in a complete randomized block design in plots of 60 m² (10x6 m).

Figure 42: Timeline of LTE Clever Cover Cropping (The Netherlands). Dark green: cover crop growing period; Black striped: main crop growing period; light green: intermediate period.

At the start of the experiment in 2016, basic soil parameters were measured, e.g. clay-content. SOM data (loss on ignition) were available at plot level over the period 2016 - 2022 from which SOC was calculated using a factor of 0.58. In 2022, bulk density was measured at treatment level and assumed constant over the experimental period. For both main crops and cover crops, default data were used for C-input and humification coefficients were used. Weather data were taken from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI). In AgroEcoSeqC, the following treatments were selected for soil and plant sampling:

T1: Vetch+Oats

T2: Vetch+Oats+Radish

T3: Fallow

4.2.3.3 LTE Organic Matter (Belgium)

The LTE Organic Matter was set up in 1959 and its objective is to compare different organic matter management methods (crop residue incorporation, livestock manure inputs, winter cover crops).

Location: Gembloux - Belgium (50°33' 54"N, 4° 41' 18"E), average rainfall: 751 mm, average annual temperature: 10.2 °C. The field experiment is conducted on a silty soil (85% silt, 12% clay, 3% sand).

At the start, six organic matter management treatments were studied. The crop rotation has evolved over time. Since 1991, classic three-year rotation has been systematically implemented as follows : sugar beet – winter wheat – winter barley (Figure 5). Various cover crops have been cultivated since the start of the experiment, e.g., vetch, mustard, phacelia, oilseed rape, oat, clover, radish, and sunflower.

Crop rotation

Figure 43: Timeline of LTE Organic Matter (Belgium).

The experimental set-up was installed on a 4.5 ha plot, comprising 6 blocks each made up of the 6 treatments studied (in each block, the order of the treatments is random). The 6 organic matter management treatments are applied in an experimental design comprising 36 plots (10 × 72m) in total, each treatment being replicated 6 times. Parameters related to soil fertility are measured annually (pH, total organic carbon (Walkley and Black), total organic nitrogen, C/N ratio, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium). Bulk density in all plots is assumed to be equal. Production parameters are also measured, i.e., crop yields, crop residues and production quality. C-input from the main crops is incorporated directly after harvest (in July for winter barley, August for winter wheat and November for sugar beet). The cover crops are frost or chemically killed during winter so they are left in the field and incorporated just before the sowing of sugar beet (with a rotary harrow). The cattle manure is spread after the harvest of winter barley in July-Augustus. In AgroEcoSeqC three treatments are included:

- T1: Exportation of all crop by-products, input of External Organic matter (cattle manure), no cover crop
- T2: Restitution of all crop by-products, no input of External Organic matter and a cover crop
- T3: Exportation of all crop by-products, no input of External Organic matter and no cover crop

4.2.3.4 New Experimental Field Fungi and Cover Cropping System (Turkey)

The newly established experiment Fungi and Cover Cropping System focuses on the use of cover crops during the winter period in arable cropping systems (Figure 6). The field experiment is conducted on a clay soil (25.44% sand, 19.28% silt, 55.28% clay, pH 7.75, 16.3 g kg⁻¹ N, 0.23 mg.kg⁻¹ plant-available P, and 610 mg.kg⁻¹ K ; Sanliurfa, Turkey (36°53'12.72"N, 38°55'15.04"E). Bulk density in all plots is assumed to be equal. The field has a history of conventional arable farming, with winterwheat and second production corn being the last commercially crop grown before the start of the experiment in 2022. The experiment consists of three treatments: cover crop, fungi + cover crop, and a control (no

Figure 44 : Timeline of the New Experimental Field Fungi and Cover Cropping System (Turkey. Dark green: cover crop growing period; Black striped: main crop growing period.

fungi, no cover crop). The cover crop species used in the study were a mixture of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and soybean (*Glycine max*), which were grown during the winter on fields designated for tomato production. Following the cover crops, tomato seeds obtained from commercial seed suppliers were sown in a greenhouse, and seedlings were transplanted to the field in May. The three treatments were replicated three times in a randomized complete block design, with plot sizes of 6.4 m² (3.2x2 m). During the experiment, no chemical fertilizers were used on the field. Instead, organic matter was applied to all plots at a rate of 54 x 10³ kg.ha⁻¹ annually (corresponding to 6.84 x 10³ kg.ha⁻¹). In AgroEcoSeqC, the following treatments are included in the tomato rotation:

T1: Cover crop (Barley and broad bean)

T2: Cover crop (Barley and broad bean) + Fungi

T3: Control

4.3 Results and Discussion

4.3.1 Assessment of optimal Rate Modifying Factor

For LTE Tillage, no difference could be assessed between tillage and no-tillage as the RothC model makes no distinction for tillage. Therefore, no positive contribution from no-tillage treatments to SOC is shown in the modelling results (Figure 7a). The C-input is treated similarly, whether incorporated in the soil, or not. If a difference between T1 and T2 would be found, then this could be ascribed to the cover crops. However, with only 2 measurements of SOC over time, it was not possible to statistically evaluate this and assess a RMF. It can be inferred though from the curves shown that the RMF would possibly be found in the higher values of the range tested.

For LTE Clever Cover Cropping, the original RothC-model was able to describe the SOC-data in the treatments VO and VOR but not in the fallow (Figure 7b). For T1 and T2, the optimal RMF was 2 and

2.1 for VO and VOR, respectively. Error bars for SOC measurements indicate high variability in the plots per treatment. This may have affected RMSE, and thus RMF. The ROTHC model was unable to model the fallow, as the measured SOC was in most years higher than modelled, except in 2021. This is probably due to the fact the fallow is, in fact, overgrown with weeds (green fallow) and therefore this treatment will not be discussed further.

For LTE Organic matter Management, the original ROTHC model modelled the treatments nicely (Figure 7c). However, in some years the measured SOC appears an outlier. Despite this, the optimal RMF was assessed and ranged from 0.2 in T3 to 0.7 in T1, respectively. As RMF is based on RMSE, this suggests that the original ROTHC model is already well equipped for modelling the LTE.

For the NEF Fungi it was found that the ROTHC model was not able to model the short-term rotation very well (Figure 7d). A minimum RMF of 3 would be required to obtain a satisfying fit with measured SOC-values in terms of RMSE. It can be inferred that the optimal RMF would probably be found in the higher values of the range tested. The experiment concerns a newly established field in an area with a short agricultural history (c. 1000 years). Therefore, it is likely that the calculated initialisation values for SOC stock do not reflect equilibrium status. As a result of this SOC-modelling may be erroneous.

a)

Figure 45: Simulation of SOC; a) LTE Tillage, T1, T2, T3; b) LTE Clever Cover cropping, T1, T2, T3. Black dots denote treatments mean SOC;

c)

d)

Figure 46: continued; c) LTE Organic Matter, T1, T2, T3; d) NEF Fungi and Cover Crops, T1, T2, T3.

4.3.2 Exploring relationships between optimal RMF and indicators soil microbiome

Since the RMF could be assessed for LTEs CCC and OM only, the exploration of the relationship between RMF and indicators for the soil microbiome is restricted to these LTEs. In the correlation analysis between RMF and indicators for the soil microbiome, several indicators were found to have a correlation factor of 0.4 (abs) for LTE CCC and LTE OM respectively. None of the indicators met the predefined threshold for the p-value of $p < 0.0001$.

Table 12: Indicators with high correlation- and p-values with the optimal RMF.

Group	Indicator	LTE CCC		LTE OM	
		correlation	p-value	correlation	p-value
Soil microbiome	M%	-0.61		0.53	<0.1
	Enchyt	0.52			
	dsDNA	-0.91	<0.002	-0.61	<0.05
	AryS	- 0.73	<0.1		
	BetaG	- 0.6		0.56	<0.1
	Xylo	- 0.64	<0.1		
	NH4	- 0.66	<0.1		
	Leu	- 0.7	<0.1		
	AcP	- 0.69	<0.1	0.48	
	AlkP	- 0.88	<0.01		
	FDA	-0.56		0.51	
	AWCD (CLPP)			0.48	
	Acc DW biomass			0.68	<0.1
Plant	Plant N	-0.72	<0.05		
	Plant P			0.74	<0.01
	Critical N			-0.67	<0.1
	Plant N demand			0.68	<0.1
Quality of OM	SOC coarse aggr.	-0.66	<0.1		
	C stock macro aggr.	-0.63	<0.1		
	WEOC macro aggr.	-0.85	<0.01		

P ₂ O ₅ in course aggr.		0.75	<0.01
SOC fine aggr.	-0.62		
C stock fine aggr.	-0.56		
P ₂ O ₅ in fine aggr.		0.73	<0.01
P ₂ O ₅ bulk soil		0.78	<0.01

Some of the indicators were directly related to the soil microbiome; some to plant quality, and others to the quality of soil organic matter. All correlations that were found for both LTEs are part of the soil microbiome group, i.e. M%, dsDNA, betaG, AcP, and FDA. Note that the LTEs show opposite orientation for the indicators M%, betaG, AcP, and FDA. Understanding why this would be so, or in general these indicators would have a direct relationship with the RMF and thus SOC-dynamics is beyond the scope of this report. Other research in AgroEcoSeqC may shed more light on this.

From the results in Table 1 it was inferred that the optimal RMF might be explained, at least partially, by the soil microbiome. However, as the threshold for p was not met, no relationships between indicator and RMF were mathematically significant. Consequently, adaptation of the ROTHC-model for the soil microbiome with a RMF_{BIO} could only be made in general terms.

4.3.3 Impact assessment

The modelling results with optimal RMF were extended from the experimental period to a period of c. 20 years using known weather data. This was done for LTEs CCC and OM, only, as RMF could not be assessed in the other experiments. For LTE CCC, the inclusion of the optimal RMF resulted in SOC loss, i.e. 3.8 t ha⁻¹ for VO to 4.5 t ha⁻¹ for VOR over the 21-year period.

For LTE OM, modelling results showed SOC gain of 8 t ha⁻¹ for the treatment with cover crops and the manure treatment showed a loss in SOC of 1 t ha⁻¹. Over this period. The control also gained SOC. However, in the interpretation of these data it needs to be considered that bulk density was not measured at treatment level and consequently calculated SOC-stocks are less reliable.

Table 13 : Impact of RMF on SOC stocks after 20 years.

LTE	Treatments	SOC% _{yr20}		SOC stock (t kg.ha ⁻¹)			
		Model version	BAU	RMF	BAU	RMF	Difference
CCC	T1: VO		1.12	0.99	33	29	4
	T2: VOR		1.06	0.91	32	27	5
OM	T1: C-input: manure		0.9	0.9	25	25	1
	T2: C-input: crop rest + CC		1.0	1.3	28	35	-8
	T3: Control, no C-input		0.7	0.8	19	22	-3

For LTE Tillage and NEF Fungi few SOC-measurements were available. From Figure 6 it may be inferred that if these data would be extrapolated over time, SOC-stock would be decreasing in all 3 treatments in LTE Tillage and increasing in T1 and T2 in NEF Fungi.

4.4 Discussion

In this research many indicators for the soil microbiome were found to have a substantial correlation with the rate related parameter RMF in the ROTHC-model. Best results in terms of correlation- and p-values were obtained for the indicator dsDNA in LTE CCC and the indicators plant-P, and P₂O₅ in course resp. fine aggregates and bulk soil in LTE OM. None of these relations were statistically significant. A correlation with RMF was also found, though less strong and reliable, for indicator dsDNA in LTE OM. The climate for both LTEs is classified as mild sea-climate (type Cfb, Köppen, <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/koppen-climate-classification-system/>), with over the year 2022 subtle differences in temperature, rainfall and evapotranspiration. A major difference between the LTEs is their soil texture. Regarding texture, LTE CCC is a sandy soil and LTE OM is a clay soil. P-fixation occurs in clay soils but not in sandy soils and clay is known to affect SOC-dynamics. This may explain that correlations on P in soil aggregates were found for LTE OM but not LTE CCC. Over the past decades, research to better understand relationships between the soil microbiome and soil P-organo-mineral-fractions is gaining attention. In particular during the winter season cover crops may have a role in this. In both LTEs SOC-contents may be close to saturation

(Porre, 2020; Simon Sail, pers. comm). From a texture point of view it would be interesting to know how saturation would be reached, in particular regarding the role of the soil microbiome in the process. To evaluate this does require plot specific data on clay%, preferably also on type of clay, and bulk density in addition to the soil microbiome.

However, the correlation results between indicators and RMF were not strong enough to ascribe them to the RMF by our predefined standards. Other factors may be more important. Application of the optimal RMF in ROTHC to model cover crop rotations showed that results may be either lower (LTE CCC, sandy soil) or higher (LTE OM, clay soil) than with BAU.

4.5 Conclusion

Indicators for the soil microbiome may be correlated to the rate parameter in SOC modelling. Given the available evidence in this research, the impact on SOC built-up may be both positive and negative. For soils with SOC-stocks near saturation, soil texture may be the major factor responsible.

4.6 Acknowledgement

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